

An aerial photograph of a university campus. In the foreground, a large, circular, modern building with a curved roof is prominent. Surrounding it are various other buildings, parking lots, and green spaces. In the background, there are rolling hills and a winding road under a clear sky.

Diamond contribution to the development of an innovative vaccine for Foot-and-Mouth Disease: a veterinary pathology of global significance

Case study report

ADDRESS

CORSO MONFORTE 15,
20122 MILAN, ITALY
<http://www.csilmilano.com/>

PREPARED FOR

Diamond Light Source Ltd

François Cesmat - Senior Information Analyst
(Consultant)

Isabelle Boscaro-Clarke - Head of
Communications, Engagement & Impact

Kat Roarty - Impact Manager

CSIL lead author

Jessica Catalano - Partner and Senior Researcher

Contributions by

Massimo Florio - CSIL and University of Milano

Raffaele Articolo - CSIL

Giulio Consiglio - CSIL

David Eggleton - University of Sussex

TABLE OF CONTENTS

- 1. Introduction 5
- 2. The role of Research Infrastructures and radiation facilities in Vaccine Development 7
 - 2.1 The role of Research Infrastructures 7
 - 2.2 The role of synchrotron light sources 8
- 3. The role of Diamond in the FMD vaccine development 11
 - 3.1 The research on FMD virus at Diamond 11
 - 3.2 The added value of Diamond 16
 - 3.3 The value of FMD-related knowledge generated at Diamond 18
- 4. Epidemiology of FMD..... 20
 - 4.1 Serotypes and geographical coverage 20
 - 4.2 FMD governance..... 23
- 5. FMD costs 26
 - 5.1 Production losses 26
 - 5.2 Cost of existing prevention and control measures 28
 - 5.3 Is vaccination a viable strategy to fight FMD?..... 31
- 6. The VLP vaccine: advantages and challenges 36
 - 6.1 New vaccines generation 36
 - 6.2 VLP advantages..... 37
 - 6.3 VLP current challenges 39
 - 6.4 What if? 40
- 7. Conclusions 42
- Annex 1. Estimating the Benefits of the VLP vaccine: underlying assumptions 44
- Annex 2. Patents’ citation analysis 47
- Annex 3. Bibliography..... 54

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Co-authorship network of publications	14
Figure 2: The geographic distribution of FMD and recent global outbreaks	22
Figure 3: Members of FMD with official status	24
Figure 4: Matches between P0 (left hand side) and Pat0 (right hand side)	48
Figure 5: Number of patents by type of patent owner	50
Figure 6: Top granted patents owners	50
Figure 7: Number of patents (granted and applications) by sectors of application (CPC classification)	50
Figure 8: Matches between authors of P0 publications (left-hand side) and Pat0 patents (right hand side)	51
Figure 9: Matches between P1 (green dots) and Pat1 (red dots)	52
Figure 10: Number of patents by jurisdiction	53
Figure 11: Number of patents (granted and application) by CPC sector	53

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: A summary of the PCP stages	25
Table 2 Estimates of production losses: evidence from literature	26
Table 3: Measures to prevent and control a FMD outbreak	28
Table 4: New generation of vaccines	36
Table 5: Inactivated vs. new generation of vaccine	38
Table 6 An overview of our estimation	41
Table 7: Our estimation: underlying assumptions	44
Table 8 The first wave of publications cited by patents	48

LIST OF BOXES

Box 1: Synchrotrons for Covid-19 research	9
Box 2 The GALVmed approach to estimate the vaccines' impacts	33
Box 3 The limitations of inactivated vaccines	34

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

BSL-3	Biosafety Level 3
DIVA	Differentiating Infected from Vaccinated Animals
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructure
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation
FMD	Foot and Mouth Disease
FMDV	Foot and Mouth Disease Virus
FMD-VLP	Foot and Mouth Disease Virus-Like-Particle vaccine
GALVmed	Global Alliance for Livestock Veterinary Medicines
GeV	Gigaelectron Volt
GF-TADs	Global Framework for the Progressive Control of Transboundary Animal Diseases
GBP	British pound sterling
HEPA	High-Efficiency Particulate Air
LMICs	Low and Middle Income Countries
LSUs	Livestock Units
MSD	Merck Sharp & Dohme
NSP	Non-structural proteins
PCP	Progressive Control Pathway
RAG	Regional Advisory Group
RI	Research infrastructures
R&D	Research and development
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
SOPs	Standard Operating Procedures
STFC	Science and Technology Facilities Council
USD	United States Dollar
VLP	Virus-Like-Particle
WOAH	World Organisation for Animal Health

1. INTRODUCTION

This study presents the results of the assessment of a **new soon to reach market Virus-Like-Particle (VLP) vaccine** – developed by Diamond Light Source Synchrotron¹ (*hereafter Diamond*) in collaboration with the Pirbright Institute, the Universities of Reading and Oxford and MSD Animal Health **to prevent Foot-and-Mouth Disease (FMD)**. The assessment specifically focuses on the benefits that would be brought about by this new vaccine (*hereafter FMD-VLP*) as compared to existing alternatives and on the role played by Diamond in its development.

FMD is a highly contagious viral disease that affects cloven-hoofed animals, including **cattle, pigs, sheep, goats, and deer**. It is caused by the FMD Virus, which belongs to the Picornaviridae family. Several viruses belong to this family, including those causing poliomyelitis and hepatitis, as well as milder illnesses such as the common cold². FMD Virus is one of the most infectious viruses³ which spreads quickly within and between animal herds through multiple routes⁴. Outbreaks can escalate rapidly, affecting large numbers of animals within a short period⁵.

According to the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH), FMD affects 77% of the global livestock population, primarily in Africa, the Middle East, Asia, and some countries in South America⁶. It manifests through **various symptoms**, which can vary in severity depending on the species, age, and immune status of the affected animals.

FMD is generally not fatal for adult animals but **leads to significant economic losses** through reduced productivity and production loss. Some of the main consequences include reduced milk production and a decline in traction power for agricultural work. This both directly impacts a farmer's income potential from milk production and has knock-on impacts by making it harder to plough fields. It poses a major threat to the livestock industry and can severely impact international trade due to strict import restrictions imposed by affected countries. The economic impact of FMD in the endemic regions of the world is estimated to be 6.5 to 21 billion USD⁷ per year (Knight-Jones, T. J. D., & Rushton, J. 2013)

The WOAH sets **international standards and guidelines** for FMD prevention, surveillance, and control, serving as a platform for member countries to share information, collaborate on research,

¹ Diamond Light Source Synchrotron is the UK's national synchrotron facility funded as a joint venture by the UK Government through the Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), in partnership with the Wellcome Trust. Established in 2002, it is operational since 2007 and it is used by more than 8,000 academic and industrial researchers across a wide range of disciplines.

² The virus of Polio also belongs to the same virus family.

³ While the interviewees cited a reproductive number (R0) as high as 80, the literature tends to use R₀ for cattle in the range of 2.52 to 14 (Bravo de Rueda et al., 2014; Orsel et al., 2005). Some small experiments (N=10) have determined much higher R₀ of infinity (Orsel et al., 2007).

⁴ These include direct contact with infected animals, contaminated objects, respiratory droplets, and aerosols.

⁵ For instance, the United Kingdom experienced two major FMD outbreaks in 1967 and 2001. In 1967, the virus killed 442,000 animals, while in 2001, public authorities had to cull over 4 million animals to contain the disease (James & Rushton, 2002).

⁶ More information available at the following links: <https://www.woah.org/en/disease/foot-and-mouth-disease/> and <https://rb.gy/9nnh7>

⁷ 4.97 to 16.05 GBP according to the exchange rate on November 20th, 2025: 1 USD = 0.76 GBP. This exchange rate is applied throughout the document.

and exchange expertise to manage FMD outbreaks. Its most important responsibility is assessing FMD status, classifying countries accordingly. Achieving FMD-free status offers trade advantages.

Several measures can be adopted to prevent and control FMD outbreaks, from surveillance and monitoring to vaccination and animal culling, often implemented in combination. Associated costs and benefits vary also in relation to country specific factors. Response time and financial costs can motivate the choice of one measure over another.

To limit the impacts of the disease **different types of vaccines are available**, primarily based on inactivated virus. However, they have limitations requiring high-security storage, a cold chain due to instability (a factor which also limits their shelf life), hindering outbreak detection due to indistinguishable antibodies, and being specific to a single FMD serotype.

The FMD-VLP vaccine, under assessment, aims to overcome these limitations, particularly in terms of manufacturing safety and the challenges related to its transportation, storage, and administration. **Diamond beamlines** were instrumental to study the virus in detail and reconstruct its structure in the first place, building also on previous work at Diamond's predecessor synchrotron light source: the Synchrotron Radiation Source (SRS) of Daresbury Laboratory. The vaccine development was reported in 2013 with a publication by Porta et. al. (2013). In 2018, in association with a translation award from the Wellcome Trust, a license to produce the vaccine was granted by the Pirbright Institute, the leader of the consortium, to the pharmaceutical company Merck Sharp & Dohme (MSD) Animal Health with the objective of initiating the commercialisation process for the vaccine. The vaccine is currently in development phase as of the end of 2023 and is expected to be brought to market in the next few years.

The assessment of the FMD-VLP vaccine project – along with the contribution provided by Diamond - was carried out by a CSIL team between May-December 2023. It draws from an **extensive desk research** (see Annex 3 for the list of consulted documents) and aimed to get a better understanding of the FMD virus and existing vaccines. In addition, **16 interviews** with various stakeholders were carried out, including researchers from Diamond, FMD researchers at universities, experts from animal health agencies and vaccine institutes, national institutes on FMD in endemic countries as well as researchers working at other synchrotron light sources. These interviews were undertaken to gather opinion on the added value of an FMD-VLP vaccine, on the role of synchrotrons in developing this vaccine as well as alternative techniques available to researchers (e.g. electron microscopy, free electron lasers).

The outcomes of this assessment are detailed in the following sections. Specifically, Section 2 provides an introduction to the role of RIs in the development of vaccines, in general, and highlights the specific contribution of synchrotron light sources. Section 3 describes the specific role of Diamond and its added value in the FMD virus research; Section 4 describes FMD covering its epidemiology, geographical spread and governance; Section 5 discusses the costs associated with FMD, including production losses and cost of prevention and control measures; Section 6 discusses the advantages of a new generation vaccine, expected challenges for its development and an estimate of potential benefits (what if scenario). Section 7 concludes.

2. THE ROLE OF RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES AND RADIATION FACILITIES IN VACCINE DEVELOPMENT

This Section discusses the role of Research infrastructure (RI) in the vaccine development and more specifically of synchrotron light sources, a specific type of RI, of which Diamond is an example.

2.1 The role of Research Infrastructures

Assessing the contribution of Diamond in the creation of an FMD-VLP vaccine requires us to understand the role of research performed thanks to RIs, and more specifically of radiation facilities in vaccine development. As defined by the European Commission, RIs are *"facilities that provide resources and services for research communities to conduct research and foster innovation. They include major scientific equipment or sets of instruments, collections, archives or scientific data, computing systems and communication networks, any other research and innovation infrastructure of a unique nature which is open to external users and are essential to achieve excellent in research and innovation."*⁸ In other words, RIs essentially act as a resource for researchers, providing them with the essential apparatus and know-how to create new knowledge and then, develop, new products and services.

The role of RIs in vaccine development has already been acknowledged by the European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures (ESFRI, 2021). Vaccine development comes with high expenditure requirements and has uncertain outcomes. Therefore, access to RIs is important to academic institutions and industry, including pharmaceutical companies, to go through the complex and resource-intensive procedure of developing new drugs. One of the most common business models - in the development of new vaccines - is based on the collaboration between public and private actors which concretely materialises in the provision of access to biomedical RIs. In practice, **RIs can support the development of a vaccine at every possible stage of its development**, from preclinical research to manufacturing and regulatory approval. Each of these stages has its own unique requirements, and various services and forms of support can be provided to address them. In the pre-clinical phase, they provide access to animals for testing and experts who know how to design and conduct experiments. They also provide laboratories and tools to help predict if a vaccine will work. When it is time for the clinical phase, RIs help find the right places to do these tests and connect with experts who can supervise them. As vaccines get closer to being manufactured, these infrastructures have the tools and know-how to contribute to researchers about how to make them in big quantities while keeping them safe and effective. Finally, they may help with all the paperwork needed to get permission to use vaccines.

RIs foster collaborative research. Each RI has its specific added value in terms of tools and techniques made available to the research community. Typically, a joint effort of different research teams and facilities is needed to undertake a complex research task such as vaccine development. Jungbluth et. al (2022) conducted an online survey⁹ on the role of RIs in vaccine development by highlighting gaps and needs in European vaccine research, particularly in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. They emphasised that no single infrastructure at the time could comprehensively address

⁸ European Commission definition. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/european-research-infrastructures_en

⁹ 33 organisations contributed to the survey, including 24 research institutes and universities, and 9 pharmaceutical companies

most of the identified needs for vaccine development. They demonstrated that the major obstacles to vaccine development concerned identifying the appropriate platform technology to produce the vaccine. The platform technology consists of two main components: the antigen expression and the vaccine formulation. Antigen expression involves creating the actual components (antigens) used in the vaccine while vaccine formulation involves determining whether an adjuvant (a substance that enhances the immune response) is needed and selecting the right delivery system for the vaccine. RIs can be extremely beneficial for these two procedures, as they can provide access to expertise and technological facilities that, for instance, can support molecular engineering of the antigens or improve the overall stability of the vaccines.

2.2 The role of synchrotron light sources

Both the survey mentioned above and the evidence collected through interviews for the present study confirm that a **major contribution to vaccine development for different pathogens comes from** a specific type of RIs, such as **synchrotron light sources**.

Synchrotrons are a specific kind of particle accelerator which work by accelerating charged particles using radio frequency cavities around a fixed circular path to near light speed. The particle beam is kept on this circular path using different types of magnets which 'bend' the beam through its many rotations in the system 'in sync' with its increasing kinetic energy. This beam can also be focussed using dipole, quadrupole or sextupole magnets. The supporting infrastructure may include linear accelerators or other synchrotrons acting as 'boosters'.

Synchrotrons conduct different kinds of analysis. The breadth of science undertaken under one roof is extremely varied and in particular, for the life sciences an extremely useful one is X-ray crystallography, which is a powerful method for determining the precise 3D structure of extremely small and complex biological entities like viruses. This technique involves producing crystals of the target molecule and using X-ray diffraction to reveal atomic-level details, enabling in-depth insights into virus structures and mechanisms. Whilst whole infectious viruses can be analysed by this method it is usual to reduce risk by using inactivated or attenuated viruses, virus like particles (if these are available) or even components of the virus such as surface glycoproteins¹⁰.

Overall, in the context of vaccine development, a synchrotron can be valuable in several ways (Malito et. al., 2015):

- **Antigen Characterisation:** Synchrotrons can be used to determine the high-resolution three-dimensional structure of antigens, such as proteins or viral particles. This structural information can help engineer more stable virus antigen to enhance shelf life and avoid the necessity of cold chains or can improve our understanding of how the antigens interact with the immune system to facilitate designing vaccines that can elicit a targeted immune response. Researchers can use synchrotron-generated X-ray crystallography or cryo-electron microscopy to obtain detailed antigen structures.

¹⁰ This information was extracted from the website of Soleil. Available at : <https://www.synchrotron-soleil.fr/en/news/soleils-contribution-understanding-viruses#:~:text=SOLEIL%20contributes%20to%20building%20a,of%20developing%20effective%2C%20appropriate%20treatments.>

- **Epitope Mapping:** Synchrotron facilities can assist in mapping epitopes, which are specific regions on an antigen that antibodies recognise. Understanding the precise locations of epitopes is essential for designing vaccines that can induce protective immune responses.
- **Formulation Studies:** When formulating vaccines, it's important to ensure that the structural integrity of antigens is maintained. Synchrotron-based techniques can be used to study the stability of antigens in various vaccine formulations, helping researchers choose the most suitable formulation that preserves antigen conformation.
- **Adjuvant Development:** Synchrotron facilities can be used to study the interactions between antigens and adjuvants, helping researchers optimise the combination for a more effective immune response.
- **Quality Control:** Synchrotron-based techniques can be used for quality control purposes to ensure that the antigens used in vaccine production meet specific structural criteria.
- **Antigen Modification:** Researchers can use synchrotron data to guide the engineering or modification of antigens to enhance their immunogenicity or stability.

These synchrotrons can also be used in combination with other facilities. For example, a synchrotron can be used in combination with a cryo electron microscope or different sample treatments.

Synchrotrons have facilitated the research underpinning many Nobel prizes (Galli, 2014). It has become a standard tool in determining protein structure with up to 90% of the structures in the Protein Data Bank being derived from data obtained using synchrotrons, according to our interviewees. Both literature (e.g. Argonne, 2021) and interviewees highlighted that synchrotrons have been useful in studying crucial biomedical innovations such as new anti-flu drugs or treatments against Covid-19. As pointed out by interviewees, research on the structures of many proteins, viruses and vaccines would not have been possible without synchrotrons.

Box 1: Synchrotrons for Covid-19 research

Synchrotrons played a crucial role in fighting COVID-19. As reported in the CERN Courier¹¹ at the end of January 2020 a structural biologist from ShanghaiTech University in China successfully solved the structure of the primary SARS-CoV-2 protease thanks to the research done at the Shanghai Synchrotron Radiation Facility (SSRF). Notably, they shared their findings by depositing the results in the global Protein Data Bank. However, the research faced an unexpected pause due to the SSRF's scheduled shutdown. In response, the Diamond team swiftly mobilised, overcoming challenges related to shipping biological samples from China during the height of the COVID-19 outbreak. Opting for a synthetic gene, the team genetically engineered Escherichia coli to produce the coronavirus protease, enabling structural determination and inhibitor screening. Eleven days later the Diamond team started experimental trials to generate protein crystals. The pivotal role of Diamond became apparent. The facility's X-ray radiation capabilities were indispensable for the rapid analysis of protein structures. By directing focused X-rays down a beamline onto a crystal, the team could analyse diffraction patterns to determine 3D electron density maps and unravel the intricate structure of the protein.

¹¹ <https://cerncourier.com/a/synchrotrons-on-the-coronavirus-frontline/>

Despite challenges, the first crystals were produced within days of receiving the synthetic gene. While initially modest, these crystals were of sufficient quality for testing on Diamond's macromolecular crystallography beamlines, highlighting the critical role of synchrotron technology in expediting COVID-19 vaccine research.

Researchers from various backgrounds, including universities, research institutions, and companies, have since then been using synchrotrons worldwide to study in details the SARS-CoV-2 virus and its evolving features. Indeed, the virus is too small to be observed with a regular light microscope, as it is smaller than visible light wavelengths. Its observation was made possible by synchrotrons. Examples of research projects carried out:

- Creating a new model of the SARS-CoV-2 virus for better understanding of its characteristics.
- Decoding the three-dimensional structure of the virus's main protease, a crucial target for drug development.
- Screening thousands of drugs for potential efficacy against the virus.
- Advancing drug development by studying viral target proteins.
- Improving RNA vaccines stability and immunogenicity
- Investigating innovative drug administration methods to mitigate side effects.
- Spatially imaging coronaviruses within cells to study virus uptake and drug interactions.
- Gaining insights into the binding processes between substances and the coronavirus.
- Mapping lung alterations in COVID-19 patients with high resolution.
- Studying damaged lung tissue from COVID-19 patients.
- Analysing aerosol particle emissions during various activities to understand their role in pathogen transmission.
- Identifying antibodies that neutralise COVID-19 variants.

Source: Authors processing¹²

Access of research teams to a synchrotron light source¹³ is allocated based on scientific merit and potential technical novelty with broadly similar processes across most facilities. Aspiring experimenters must prepare a proposal making the scientific case for the experiment which is subject to peer and committee review. Facility technicians will also be consulted about the technical viability of the proposal. Proposals must demonstrate both scientific merit and technical viability to be approved. If a proposal is approved, the facility will work with the successful applicants to make the necessary adaptations to the experiment and instruments to perform the work. After the completion of the session scheduled in a given proposal, many facilities require the production of an experimental report outlining the project results.

Our interviewees from other synchrotron light sources facilities stated it is human factors that dictate the success of a scientific collaboration. Even if advanced technical assets are present, it is the human capital that unlocks the facility's experimental potential. Convenience in terms of geography and timing are also factors governing where users choose to do experiments. Diamond has clear advantages in this perspective, as discussed in the following Section.

¹² On the basis of information extracted from the following website: <https://www.sni-portal.de/en/user-committees/committee-research-with-synchrotron-radiation/research-with-synchrotron-radiation/synchrotrons-for-corona-research>

¹³ Such access is referred to within the research community as access to 'beamtime'

3. THE ROLE OF DIAMOND IN THE FMD VACCINE DEVELOPMENT

This Section outlines the role played by Diamond in the FMD vaccine development by describing the kind of research performed and argues on the added role played by this synchrotron as compared to available alternatives.

3.1 The research on FMD virus at Diamond

The initial research on the structure of the FMD virus was performed at Daresbury radiation facility, also in the UK.

The Synchrotron Radiation Source (SRS) at Daresbury Laboratory was an X-Ray based synchrotron that operated from 1981 to 2008. It was the world's first 'second generation' synchrotron¹⁴ (STFC, 2017, 2010). Over its experimental lifetime its X-Ray crystallography enabled scientists to determine the structure of portions of several viruses including HIV/AIDS and Avian flu. However, the groundbreaking work it enabled for FMDV is most relevant for this report. STFC (2010) have stated that understanding the structure of FMDV would not have been possible without SRS.

The research was cutting edge at that time. Handling live FMDV even in a crystal lattice required permission from the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food to transport samples and was conditional on the constant presence of a disease security officer and no violation of an agreed protocol (Fry et al., 1993). Data collection used a wavelength (λ) of 1.488Å (0.1488nm) and 0.9Å (0.09nm) for comparative purposes which showed an enhanced signal to noise ratio and crystal lifetime (Fry et al., 1993). The work was regarded as so cutting-edge, even the methods used to obtain the structural data were publishable (Fry et al., 1993). Subsequent follow-up work at Daresbury performed deeper examinations of viral structures (Fry et al., 2005), examined the differences between FMDV serotypes (Lea et al., 1995), differences within the A22 serotype (Curry et al., 1996), and how the FMDV binds to cells (Fry et al., 1999; Logan et al., 1993).

Moreover, the original paper showing the structure of FMDV explicitly stated that this work would have applications in the development of novel vaccines and anti-viral drugs (Acharya et al., 1989). Through understanding of the structure of a virus, it is possible to identify potential targets for drugs that can inhibit virus reproduction or to bio-engineer VLP structures that cannot induce disease. It was initially estimated that a new vaccine could deliver conservative benefits of £84 million should there be a repeat of the 2001 UK foot and mouth disease outbreak¹⁵ from an initial investment of tens of thousands of pounds (STFC, 2010).

It is apparent that the work at Diamond to create a VLP vaccine continues the work started at SRS. Many of the researchers from the FMDV work at SRS are also involved in the work conducted at Diamond; this is especially important because Diamond was intended as the replacement for SRS at Daresbury Laboratory once it had reached end of life and demonstrates that the location change has not led to a significant shift in research focus (Dickson, 1997; STFC, 2017).

¹⁴ It was referred to in these terms because the first generation essentially used radiation that was a byproducts of bending magnets at high energy physics facilities whereas the second generation were dedicated sources (Robinson, 2015).

¹⁵ STFC (2010) made a conservative estimate of a 1% saving from the estimated costs of £8.4 billion (NAO, 2002).

Early work on novel FMDV vaccines investigated a peptide-based vaccine but work transitioned to a VLP technology as the evidence found a peptide-based technology to be less effective even compared to an inactivated virus vaccine (Sobrino et al., 2001, 1999); this opinion was shared by the interviewees as the quote below demonstrates:

“Until this point (the start of the collaboration with Pirbright), the research had primarily focussed on peptide-based vaccines, which were tested on small animals. These peptide vaccines did not generate the necessary immune response. This led us to decide to develop a vaccine that closely mimicked the virus itself rather than just its subunits. This marked the beginning of the work on Virus-Like Particle technology.”

Quotes from interviews

There was also a change in the composition of the collaboration, brought about by the withdrawal of Wellcome Biotech from animal health research. This led to the Pirbright Institute joining the collaboration as the quote below shows:

“In 1989, Stuart and his team successfully published the structure of FMDV. However, around the same time, Wellcome (Biotech) discontinued its involvement in animal health research. As a result, the work on the potential vaccine was relocated marking the beginning of a collaboration with the Pirbright Institute.”

Quotes from interviews

It is noted that the article on the structure of FMDV had a co-authorship from Wellcome Biotech¹⁶ and live virus crystal samples were contained at a Wellcome Biotech facility before transport to Daresbury (Acharya et al., 1989; Fry et al., 1993). The withdrawal of Wellcome Biotech led to the Pirbright Institute taking a more prominent role in the work.

The contribution provided by Diamond to the development of the FMD-VLP vaccine under assessment is perceived by the research community to be very significant.

Diamond is in fact a good example of a facility described above. Notably Diamond has a fine microfocus beam (beamline I24) and to measure small protein crystals well suited to the FMDV challenge together with a contained beamline (IO3) that can work with samples up to CL3 and having highly parallel beam. Both beamline have ‘in-situ’ capability so that a plate containing virus crystals can be put directly in the beam. This prevents un-necessary handling of infectious material and avoids damaging delicate crystals.

According to interviewees, the introduction of electron microscopy had a transformative impact on structural biology, and Diamond's decision to incorporate this technology in its offer, approximately a decade ago, proved to be a valuable asset in the development of the FMD-VLP in terms of

¹⁶ Wellcome Biotech is legally distinct from the Wellcome Trust.

integration of different analytical tools. Interviewees highlighted the **complementary roles played by both X-ray crystallography and electron microscopy** in their work. The complementarity of the two tools formed a unique and unparalleled combination, enabling a multidimensional approach and fostering a more comprehensive understanding of the structure of the FMDV. CryoEM requires less material, the sample does not have to form crystals and it can give a better idea of heterogeneity.

Since the beginning of the project, two beamlines at Diamond were considered by the researchers involved in the FMD study to be particularly useful for offering a good resolution of FMDV because of their parallel beams: I03 and I24. I03 is a special beamline that can adjust its light, with a range from short to long wavelengths¹⁷. The focused light beam is quite small, measuring 90 x 30 micrometers. This beamline is designed for experiments with frozen samples, using standard pins and containers. This beamline is equipped to handle experiments with biological substances of Hazard Groups 3, providing safety measures. I24 is a specialised microfocus beamline designed for macromolecular crystallography (MX). It holds the distinction of being the first of its kind in Europe and has been in operation since 2008. In 2015/2016, the beamline underwent a complete reconstruction, featuring a new dual goniometer end station and new mirrors. This beamline stands out for its exceptionally high flux densities, making it ideal for studying the structure of viruses, membrane proteins, and even tiny microcrystals. It combines advanced optics, sophisticated detectors, and state-of-the-art automation systems, allowing for precise sample positioning, efficient data collection, and detailed analysis.¹⁸

From 2010 to 2013, the collaboration completed a £1.3 million Wellcome Trust funded project under the translational science grant scheme to stabilize the capsid structure of the VLP based vaccine¹⁹; this provides a useful starting point for analysis. Web of Science publication data captures the academic outputs from this project and this can be used as a starting point for mapping this collaboration which is shown below in **Error! Reference source not found..** This was supplemented with additional data based on funding acknowledgements²⁰ and other information available from the Diamond website. To conclude, it is evident that Diamond has been central to this collaboration.

¹⁷ ranging from 0.6 to 2.48 Å. Usually, it operates at a standard wavelength of 0.976 Å.

¹⁸ Source: www.diamond.ac.uk/Instruments/Mx/I03.html and www.diamond.ac.uk/Instruments/Mx/I24.html

¹⁹ The grant number is formally 089755/Z/09/Z but publication data tends refers to the grant as '089755'

²⁰ Acknowledgements data identified DEFRA funding (2811). While further Wellcome Trust funding was identified as being linked to FMDV research, the evidence indicates that most outputs related to other viruses (101122/Z/13/Z).

Figure 1: Co-authorship network of publications

Source: Authors Note: The figure includes publications acknowledging funding from Wellcome Trust grant number '089755' over time supplemented with publication data available from the Diamond website. Original data gathered from Web of Science and mapped using VOSviewer

Out of the articles examined for this work, three explicitly stated that they used Diamond: Titan Krios²¹ (Kotecha et al., 2018) and I24 (Kotecha et al., 2015; Porta et al., 2013a). The research began with what may be considered as a first phase in terms of solving purification challenges for FMDV (Seago et al., 2012). While it offered applications in traditional vaccines, this article explicitly stated that the methodology could also be used for next-generation 'empty-capsid vaccines' (ie. A VLP vaccine) (Seago et al., 2012).

This research rapidly transitioned into further refinement work to produce these empty capsids efficiently and to demonstrate a proof of concept. The efficient production method was achieved using insect cells (Porta et al., 2013b). The proof of concept demonstrated significant protection during a challenge trial 34 weeks post-immunisation (Porta et al., 2013a). Two types of empty capsid were used – A22-wt (wild type FMDV) and A22-H2093C²² (an FMDV capsid specially engineered to be more stable). The issue was that the wild-type capsids were unstable. One of the interviewees, who was part of the collaboration, best articulated the issue:

²¹ This is a suite of fully automated cryo-electron microscopes. Cryogenic electron microscopy (cryo-EM) and cryogenic electron tomography data can be collected with these facilities. The collaboration did not use these facilities in the 2013 work as the technology was not available until 2017.

²² More specifically histidine 93 in VP2 was changed into cysteine (H2093C). This had the effect of creating strong disulphide bonds between neighboring groups of five proteins.

“Virus-like particles are even less stable than classic vaccine. So basically the moment you produce them they fall apart... And the only thing you can do on the molecular level is to make amino acid mutations such that you create bridges in those particles that lock the different building blocks together so the virus-like particle cannot fall apart. Only capsids that are intact induce immunity; once it falls apart (there’s) no immunity, no protection, nothing.”

Quotes from interviews

The contribution by Diamond to this work was critical in understanding how and where the capsids were falling apart. According to interviewees based in the collaboration, I24 was specifically used for this work due to its parallel beams which allowed a good resolution of the capsids. Porta et al. (2013a) shows the resolution facilitated by I24, specifically its micro-focus beamline used to create a 20x20µm² beam at a wavelength (λ) of 0.9778Å (0.09778nm). I24 allowed researchers to identify where they could make a targeted engineering intervention to modify the capsid to enhance its stability. This is regarded by the scientific community as one of the highlights of the I24 beamline programme (Allan et al., 2015).

The challenge trial²³ outlined in the article also shows a clear immune response (Porta et al., 2013a). There were three groups in the challenge, 1) four cows vaccinated with A-22 wild-type capsids, 2) four cows vaccinated with A22-H2093C capsids, and 3) two non-vaccinated cows acting as a control. There were significant benefits to the treated animals compared to the non-treated ones, as well as enhanced benefits for cattle treated with the A22-H2093C compared to wild-type.

Diamond was also crucial in follow-up work in this area (Kotecha et al., 2015). This work used I24 again to confirm the effect of strengthening capsid interfaces for two of the least stable FMD VLP vaccine candidates, namely those for the O and SAT2 serotypes. For this work, the I24 micro-focus beamline was again employed using either a 20x20µm² or a 50x50µm² beam depending on crystal size at a wavelength (λ) of 0.9778Å (0.09778nm). I24 was the only facility used to provide experimental confirmation of *in silico* predictions.

The most recent article from this research that is accessible used a relatively new Diamond facility – Titan Krios operating in a cryo-electron microscopy mode (Kotecha et al., 2018). This facility removes the need for crystals so scientists can collect data much more quickly compared to using X-ray crystallography as samples must be grown in crystalline structures. It also allows ‘movie’ creation to correct for any particle ‘drifting’. Titan Krios was used in combination with a Tecnai F30 ‘Polara’ at the University of Oxford and the interviewees stated that this multidimensional approach allowed for a more comprehensive understanding of capsid structures. These facilities enabled new understandings of a chimeric clone of the SAT2 and O serotypes that displayed SAT2 characteristics but with a much greater thermostability – this was referred to as SAT2-O1K (Kotecha et al., 2018). This

²³ A challenge trial is essentially where participants are deliberately exposed to a pathogen to test the efficacy of a treatment or vaccine versus non-treatment or non-vaccination. This allows researchers to study disease progression in a controlled environment.

represents further work enabled by Diamond that may help enhance the thermostability and efficacy of future VLP vaccines against other serotypes; an important factor when one considers that FMD endemic areas also may have challenges with reliable cold chains.

3.2 The added value of Diamond

As part of our analysis, we investigated the "what if scenario" i.e. what would have happened in case Diamond had not supported the research on the VLP vaccine. We explored what alternative facilities the collaboration would have used to accomplish the work if Diamond were not available. Within this we assumed that 1) SRS would still have been closed at end of life without Diamond acting as a replacement, 2) no alternative facility is constructed to fill this gap in the UK research infrastructure 'offering'.

The articles published gathered data from two apparatus at Diamond; these were the I24 beamline and a Titan Krios operating in combination with a Tecnai F30 'Polara' at the University of Oxford (Kotecha et al., 2018, 2015; Porta et al., 2013a). The research team examined a catalogue of European light sources to determine whether suitable alternatives existed that matched the characteristics of I24. It must be noted that at commissioning in 2008, I24 was the first beamline of its kind in Europe so there was a period in which there was no alternative (Diamond Light Source, 2020). At the time of data collection for the Porta et al. (2013a) article which appears to have been pre-2013, no alternative facility appears to have existed.

From the alternatives identified MASSIF-1, ID23-1, and MASSIF-3 at ESRF were not commissioned until 2014 and, except for MASSIF-1, cannot currently support the beam sizes used for the research ($20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}^2$ and $50 \times 50 \mu\text{m}^2$) (ESRF, 2023a, 2023b, 2022). Of the ESRF facilities identified, ID30B appears to be the most likely alternative but was not commissioned until 2015 (McCarthy et al., 2018). At the laboratory SOLEIL, PROXIMA 1 in combination with PX2-A would also appear suitable but this combination was not available until 2013 (Duran et al., 2013). At ALBA the currently under construction XAIRA may provide an alternative machine upon full commissioning at the end of 2023 (Martin-Garcia et al., 2022), but clearly this could not have acted as an alternative to I24 in 2012/2013. A more promising alternative was BL13-XALOC at ALBA which was in operation in 2012/2013 when the data collection underlying the Porta et al. (2013a) article took place (Juanhuix et al., 2014); although there are some queries over its technical suitability as this machine is unable to support the same beam size. Moreover, there would have been additional challenges associated with transporting FMDV samples across international borders (University of Birmingham, 2022).

Without the Titan Krios facility at Diamond, while it was used in combination with the Tecnai F30 'Polara' at the University of Oxford on a complementary basis, the data collection underpinning the Kotecha et al. (2018) article may have still been partially achievable using alternative Titan Krios machines. Even if no alternative Titan Krios could be identified²⁴, the work could still have been completed using solely the Oxford 'Polara', offering however a much lower resolution so this would have limited the impact. Perhaps most importantly, the work would have been much less convenient for the researchers. According to our interviewees researchers generally like to conduct experimentation close to their home institution where possible. In this case, journeys of less than 100

²⁴ Diamond did not acquire this number of Titan until 2020; the full suite was achieved only then.

kilometres for the main collaborators could have turned into trips of the order of 1,000 kilometres requiring much more planning. This is an area where Diamond held a distinct advantage over other facilities as it is closely located to both Oxford and Reading Universities and the Pirbright Institute. It can therefore act as a key experimental 'focal point' for researchers across the Thames Valley and further afield within the South East of England.

"Even if everything is there technically it's the relationships and convenience factor that's important.

Diamond had the technology, relationships, and maybe the redundancy side or capacity wasn't there or wasn't important enough to matter.

Maybe Diamond is better placed with its network of relationships for this specific vaccine.

People don't want to travel unless they have to."

Quotes from interviews

The desk research conducted for this research indicated that there is a strong consensus indicating that, given the knowledge, research teams and technological facilities available at that time, if Diamond were not available the research very likely would not have been possible and the vaccine under assessment would not exist. No single alternative exists that would have achieved the same research; several facilities would have to be used in combination and this would have created its own challenges associated with transportation of samples across international borders. During the interviews with technical experts, other facilities identified above were explicitly offered as alternatives including at ESRF, ALBA, and SwissFEL. This supplemented the desk research and allowed the study to tap into world-leading technical judgement on the suitability of these alternatives. In all cases the interviewees stated that these alternative facilities would have been inadequate due to the lack of complementarity between human and technical assets and the network of uses which are instead provided by Diamond. Even if the alternative facilities now explored above existed at the time, the unique relationship could not be replicated very easily. The quote below from an interviewee at another laboratory demonstrates that this complementarity was key for realising this research:

"Is Diamond truly the only place where this work could be done? No.

Is it the network effect that makes it possible? Maybe yes.

In my experience relationships are 50% of the game. 50% is the machine, maybe 10% is special skills within the lab, 50% this unique relationship is unique and irreplaceable."

Quotes from interviews

In particular, the high intensity of collaboration between Diamond and its scientific users was also considered by interviewees to be a key reason for the successful development of this VLP vaccine.

They outlined two approaches taken by some synchrotron light sources in their interactions with users. The first approach is characterised by the facility serving the user solely to obtain data and results, this marking the conclusion of the relationship. The second approach, exemplified by Diamond, involves a more enduring and continuous collaboration. In this model, Diamond dedicates substantial resources to establish a robust and continuous working relationship with its users. According to interviewees, Diamond's efforts are so extensive that they eliminate the boundary between the facility and the user. According to the interviewees, this intensity of collaboration is stronger at Diamond than at other synchrotron light sources facilities in Europe. It is the eclectic mix of Diamond's technical assets coupled with its complementary assets of a highly capable workforce and high intensity approach towards collaboration that made the VLP vaccine technically viable. The quotes below exemplifies the situation at Diamond compared to elsewhere:

"You can just serve the user, and the user comes and gets some results, goes home and that's it. Or you can collaborate in a more sustained and continuous way..."

The impression I had of Diamond as compared to some other European light sources is that I saw some external groups heavily engaged inside the facility... the intensity of the collaboration was stronger than elsewhere; and I think this was particularly prominent in the bio area."

Quotes from interviews

Beyond the available technology and a capable workforce, a sheer scientific interest in the topic is the final element of the unique mix that supported the vaccine development. This is personified by the lead scientist on a project. There are several examples of such lead scientists linked to projects based at Diamond (Nicholls *et al.*, 2008; Doré *et al.*, 2014)²⁵. For research on FMDV, Prof David Stuart, Director of Life Sciences at Diamond was identified as a key player in the development of the VLP vaccine by the interviewees.

Overall, the evidence collected point to the critical contribution of Diamond to the development of the new vaccine, made possible by the unique combination of a state-of-art technological facility, a dedicated and motivated research team, and scientific leadership.

In the remaining sections of the report we discuss the potential impact of the new vaccine. This requires some background data about epidemiology and economic issues at stake.

3.3 The value of FMD-related knowledge generated at Diamond

To complement our analysis on the role played by Diamond, we carried out a citation analysis allowing us to track the additional scientific knowledge or innovations triggered by the body of knowledge stemming from the use of Diamond's beamlines for the purpose FMD research²⁶. This knowledge is embedded in scientific publications authored by Diamond synchrotron direct users

²⁵ In addition, see also <https://www.diamond.ac.uk/Home/News/LatestNews/17-07-13.html>

²⁶ The analysis was inspired by Catalano et al 2020 and 2021.

(first wave knowledge) as well as in publications (second wave) citing articles written by Diamond direct users. The analysis specifically looks at the extent to which these publications are cited in patent's documents and have, therefore, contributed to generate innovations.

The methodology adopted for this analysis as well as detailed findings are presented in Annex 2.

Overall, we found that 8 out of 11 papers on FMD vaccine published between 2009 and 2018 by Diamond's users have been cited by 30 patents, out of which 15 are granted patents and the other 15 are patent applications. These are classified into a relatively wide number of subject categories, which mainly pertain to the fields of microbiology, molecular biology and general chemistry and biochemistry. Overall, they belong to 4 distinct jurisdictions: 14 granted patents have their jurisdiction in the United States, while one was filed under the European Patent Office. Regarding the 15 patent applications instead, 14 have been filed under the international patent system while one under the Korean Patent Office.

Looking at the second wave of knowledge, we found that the 11 publications authored by Diamond's users were cited by 474 unique P1 publications. Out of these, 69 were later mentioned in 164 distinct patents (90 patent applications and 73 granted patents, while for one patent the status is unknown). The sectors of application of these patents are mostly the same found for Pat0 patents.

4. EPIDEMIOLOGY OF FMD

This section introduces Foot-and-Mouth Disease from both **epidemiological and geographic perspectives**. It also describes the current FMD control strategy, – the actors responsible for its monitoring, as well as existing prevention measures. These details are crucial to understand the potential impact that a new VLP vaccine could make to controlling FMD as well as to identify the regions of the world where the benefits of such a vaccine would be maximised.

4.1 Serotypes and geographical coverage

FMD presents a complex challenge due to the presence of different serotypes with varied geographical distributions. Understanding serotype-specific immunity, accurate diagnosis, and monitoring systems are vital for effective FMD control.

FMD is caused by **seven main serotypes** of the Foot and Mouth Disease Virus classified within the genus Aphthovirus of the Picornaviridae: O, A, C, Asia 1, SAT 1, SAT 2, and SAT 3. Each serotype has multiple strains, and the dominant strain is geographically dependent. The abundance of variants within FMD virus can be attributed to its intrinsic instability²⁷. The presence of multiple serotypes presents challenges for FMD management in vaccine development as immunity to FMD is serotype-specific, meaning that animals previously exposed or vaccinated with one serotype may not be protected against infection by a different serotype. Regions may be affected by a combination of circulating serotypes, and this complicates any vaccination campaigns. Most current vaccines protect against one serotype, but not necessarily all the strains of this specific serotype (see Section 5 for more details). Finally, the presence of multiple serotypes requires the availability of accurate diagnosis and monitoring systems. This information is vital for disease surveillance, outbreak investigations, and epidemiological studies, enabling targeted control measures and tracking the spread of the disease.

Figure 1 below shows the **geographic distribution of each serotype** of the virus according to the World Reference Lab for FMD. Countries are classified into pools, which are defined as “virus ecosystems that maintain specific FMD virus strains”²⁸. **Seven endemic pools have been identified** by the Global Framework for the Progressive Control of Transboundary Animal Diseases (GF-TADs)²⁹. North Africa is not considered a pool on its own because it does not present different FMD serotypes than Eastern Africa but data for this region is extracted given its specific risk to FMD-free countries in Southern Europe (World Reference Laboratory for Foot-and-Mouth Disease, 2023). The countries that are not reported are considered by the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH) to be ‘FMD-free’ (see Section 4.2 for more details).

²⁷ This is driven by three mechanisms. Firstly, the virus's RNA replication process is prone to errors, resulting in the creation of slightly altered viral versions. Secondly, FMD viruses can engage in genetic recombination when co-infecting a host with other viruses, further diversifying their genetic makeup. Thirdly, variations in host immune systems and other factors can influence viral replication and transmission, leading to distinct viral strains in different host populations. These factors collectively contribute to the extensive diversity observed among FMD virus variants WOAHO technical disease card of FMD. Available at: <https://www.woah.org/app/uploads/2021/09/foot-and-mouth-disease-1.pdf>

²⁸ See presentation of the World Reference Lab for Foot-and-Mouth Disease at the following link: https://rr-asia.woah.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/wrl_global-fmd-situation_dk.pdf

²⁹ A joint initiative between WOAHO and FAO to facilitate international collaboration on FMD

FMD is widespread throughout **Asia, Africa, and the Middle East**, while most countries in Latin America are recognised as FMD-free through zoning measures, with or without vaccination. According to the WOAAH, this highly contagious disease affects approximately 77% of the global livestock population, primarily in Africa, the Middle East, and Asia, and few countries (e.g. Ecuador and Venezuela) in South America³⁰. Even if countries that are currently free from FMD without vaccination face constant threats of an incursion, the financial burden of FMD prevention and control falls predominantly on low-income and lower-middle-income countries. Africa incurs the highest expenses, making up 50% of the total costs, followed by Eurasia, which accounts for 33% of the total expenses³¹. Figure 2 below shows the current status of FMD outbreaks³²:

³⁰ Information available at the following link: <https://www.woah.org/en/disease/foot-and-mouth-disease/>

³¹ This information is reported on the WOAAH website. Available at: [website https://www.woah.org/en/disease/foot-and-mouth-disease/#:~:text=Geographical%20distribution,either%20with%20or%20without%20vaccination.](https://www.woah.org/en/disease/foot-and-mouth-disease/#:~:text=Geographical%20distribution,either%20with%20or%20without%20vaccination.)

³² This data is drawn from the most recent Foot-and-Mouth Quarterly report in April-June 2023 concerning the seven pools and the presence of new outbreaks in the media between April and June 2023

Figure 2: The geographic distribution of FMD and recent global outbreaks

July 2023

New headline events reported April to June 2023 are highlighted in red. Endemic pools are highlighted in orange.

REGION/COUNTRY	SEROTYPES
POOL 1: Southeast Asia / Central Asia / East Asia	
Cambodia, China, Hong Kong, Taiwan, Indonesia, Democratic People's Republic of Korea, Republic of Korea, Lao People's Democratic Republic, Malaysia, Mongolia, Myanmar, Russian Federation, Thailand, Viet Nam	A, Asia 1 and O
POOL 2: South Asia	
Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Mauritius, Nepal, Sri Lanka	A, Asia 1 and O
POOL 3: West Eurasia and Middle East	
Afghanistan, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Bahrain, Georgia, Iran (Islamic Republic of), Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Kuwait, Kyrgyzstan, Lebanon, Oman, Pakistan, Palestine, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Syrian Arab Republic, Tajikistan, Turkey, Turkmenistan, United Arab Emirates, Uzbekistan	A, Asia 1 and O (SAT 2)
POOL 4: North and Eastern Africa	
Algeria, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia, Burundi, Comoros, Djibouti, Egypt3, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Kenya, Rwanda, Somalia, South Sudan, Sudan, Uganda, United Republic of Tanzania, Yemen	O, A, SAT 1, SAT 2 and SAT 3
POOL 5: West/Central Africa	
Benin, Burkina Faso, Cabo Verde, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Chad, Congo, Côte d'Ivoire, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Mauritania, Niger, Nigeria, Sao Tome and Principe, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Togo	O, A, SAT 1 and SAT 2
POOL 6: Southern Africa	
Angola, Botswana, Malawi, Mozambique, Namibia, South Africa, Zambia, Zimbabwe	SAT 1, SAT 2 and SAT 3 (O ⁴ , A)
POOL 7: South America	
Venezuela (Bolivarian Republic of)	O and A

Source: Authors processing of World Reference Laboratory for Foot-and-Mouth Disease (2023)³³.

³³ For more details see <https://www.fao.org/3/cc7859en/cc7859en.pdf>

The high infectivity and major potential adverse impacts of FMD necessitates collaborative efforts for its management and prevention. FMD-free countries are also heavily incentivised to collaborate because the presence of FMD in other countries in their region represents a major threat.

4.2 FMD governance

The **World Organisation for Animal Health** plays a central role in coordinating international efforts to control animal diseases. It establishes international standards, guidelines, and recommendations for FMD prevention, surveillance, and control. It provides a platform for member countries to share information, collaborate on research, and exchange expertise in managing FMD outbreaks. As such it acts as both a governance mechanism and as a catalyst for international FMD work.

One of the most important responsibilities of the WOAHA is to assess the FMD status and classify countries or zones within countries accordingly. It is highly advantageous for countries to achieve FMD-free status if possible as they can benefit from certain trade advantages³⁴. FMD-free countries often implement strict surveillance, vaccination, and import control measures to maintain their FMD-free status. Given the difficulties to deal with the virus, one of the WOAHA's main activities is supporting developing countries to enhance their veterinary capacity and comply with international standards to control FMD outbreaks.

Among the 79 member countries and territories of the WOAHA with an official FMD status, 64 are acknowledged as being free from FMD without the need for vaccination. There are 11 countries that have regions where vaccination against FMD is not carried out. Out of these, 7 countries also have regions where vaccination is practiced. Furthermore, 2 countries exclusively have regions where FMD vaccination is practiced. Lastly, there are only two countries (Indonesia and Kazakhstan) where the suspension of FMD-free status has been reported. Several other countries are recognised as having zones that are free with or without vaccination. Over 100 countries are still not considered as FMD free. This information is summarised in Figure 2 below.³⁵

³⁴ Countries classified as FMD-free reached the full eradication of the virus and are, thus, no longer subject to trade restrictions. Most of the countries that currently hold the FMD free status were previously affected by the virus and thus involved in prevention and control activities. They started from an endemic situation and progressively implemented virus control campaigns to reach the FMD-free status.

³⁵ For more details see <https://www.woah.org/en/disease/foot-and-mouth-disease/#ui-id-2>

Figure 3: Members of FMD with official status

Source: WOAH website

WOAH together with FAO developed the Global Framework for the Progressive Control of Transboundary Animal Diseases (GF-TADs) to help countries progress closer to FMD-free status. It aims to improve prevention, surveillance, and control measures through the sharing of best practices, research, and resources among countries.

The main tool of GF-TADs is the **Progressive Control Pathway (PCP)** for FMD, which aims to help countries in managing FMD outbreaks. This tool categorises countries into different stages that describe the FMD risk level and potential policy options to mitigate the impact of outbreaks. Several interviewees noted increased global awareness of FMD due to the PCP framework, which contributes effectively in developing strategies against the disease. The PCP stages are summarised in Table 1 below:

Table 1: A summary of the PCP stages

STAGE	CHARACTERISTICS
0	Uncontrolled FMD risk with insufficient information. Countries in this stage need to conduct a comprehensive study on FMD epidemiology to progress to the next stage.
1	Countries have identified risks and control options. Understanding FMD epidemiology and active monitoring for FMD virus transmission are essential preconditions for the control of the virus. To advance to the next stage, countries must develop a risk based FMD control plan.
2	Countries are implementing control plans, with a monitoring and evaluation system in place. Progression to the next stage requires the development of a comprehensive strategy to eliminate FMD.
3	Countries implement control strategies to eliminate FMD circulation. Measures target critical control points in value chains to reduce the risk of FMD entry and spread. Domestic livestock should be free from endemic FMD before moving to the next stage.
4 and 5	Countries maintain zero circulation and incursions, allowing them to apply for an official WOAHP status, either free from vaccination or without vaccination.

Source: Authors

In the context of FMD governance, the regulatory landscape significantly influences the approval and adoption of new vaccines. The regulatory processes often differ between regions with well-established regulatory frameworks, such as in Europe and the United States, and those where the frameworks are comparatively less well-established such as in Low- and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs). **Several LMICs face challenges in developing robust yet efficient regulatory processes.** As a result, it can be extremely challenging to get regulatory approval in LMICs when new technologies are employed in products, potentially slowing down the introduction of new vaccines like the VLP vaccine examined in this report. Recognition of rigorous standards and safety assessments in Europe and the U.S. can streamline the approval process in LMICs, enhancing the product's global acceptance. In this regard, interviewees point out that the commercialisation process for the VLP vaccine is expected to be relatively smooth due to the close antigen similarity to inactivated vaccines already on the market. According to one of the regulatory experts interviewed as part of this research, a successful outcome from the 'standard cattle potency test' will lead to regulatory approval.

5. FMD COSTS

FMD is not usually fatal for adult animals, but it can cause several economic losses – which according to the available literature – mostly distinguish into **production losses** and **costs of prevention and control measures**. This section provides a (non-exhaustive) overview of possible estimates of these costs drawing on the existing literature on FMD. Also, it argues on the vaccination strategy as a viable investment to fight FMD.

5.1 Production losses

Foot and mouth disease **affects animal production in many ways**, such as (i) reducing the milk yields in dairy livestock and increasing the risk of mastitis; (ii) increasing rates of abortions and mortalities along with a reduction in fertility; (iii) inducing lameness that prevents animals from being used for draught power to till land, harvest crops or transport goods; (iv) causing weight loss due to a direct decline in feed intake. These consequences result in **economic losses for farms** which are widely documented in the literature (see Table below for some examples). However, the magnitude and occurrence of these losses depend on various factors, such as animal species, regional density, implementation of control measures, farmers' structures, serotype types, outbreak occurrences, leading to high variation in the reported figures.

Table 2 Estimates of production losses: evidence from literature

PRODUCTION LOSSES	ESTIMATES FROM LITERATURE
Reduction of milk production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The milk loss in the 60-days of observation is estimated to be 51.8% of potential production for lactating cattle and 55.4% for lactating buffalo. The total milk loss for the lactating animals (in total 197) was estimated to be 20.136 USD³⁶, assuming 0.52 and 0.47 USD³⁷/litre, respectively for cattle and buffalo (see Ferrari et al 2013). ▪ The mean daily milk loss per animal range from 0.7 to 17.4 kg per cow per day. The average milk losses per farm is estimated to be 1,063 USD³⁸ (with a range of 6–14,688 USD³⁹ per farm) or 19 USD⁴⁰ per animal (see Chanchaidechachai, T. et al 2022). ▪ Approximately 3,508 million litres per year, about 6.5% of the total annual milk production (Forman et al 2009) ▪ 20–44% milk yield loss in cows, and 19.6% losses in sheep (Senturk, B., & Yalcin, C. 2005). ▪ Milk production losses are between 5 and 20% depending on the farming system (Lyons et. al., 2015) ▪ Chronic FMD typically reduces milk yields by 80% (Knight-Jones, T. J. D., & Rushton, J. 2013).
Increase of abortions and mortalities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The average mortality losses is estimated to be 532 USD⁴¹ per farm (with a range of 0–6,286 USD⁴² per farm) or 18 USD⁴³ per animal (Chanchaidechachai, T. et al 2022)

³⁶ 15.90 GBP
³⁷ 0.41 and 0.37 GBP
³⁸ 839.77 GBP
³⁹ 4,740 GBP – 11,603 GBP
⁴⁰ 15 GBP
⁴¹ 420.28 GBP
⁴² 0-4,966 GBP
⁴³ 14.22 GBP

PRODUCTION LOSSES	ESTIMATES FROM LITERATURE
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The median values of increase in the mortality rate due to FMD is 1–5% in adult cattle, 5–20% in young cattle, 2% in sheep and goats and 10–15% in lambs and kids (Senturk, B., & Yalcin, C. 2005). ▪ Mortality amongst young stock is typically 2–3% (Rufael T., et al 2008) ▪ An increase in the abortion rate from 0% to 28.8% (Senturk, B., & Yalcin, C. 2005).
Reduction in traction power	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ A study of an outbreak of FMD in Ethiopia indicated that cattle, sheep and goats were affected by the disease. Affected farmers reported losses in milk production and loss in draught power production of approximately twenty days (James, A. D., & Rushton, J. 2002).
Weight losses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Between 10%-25% depending on the species and breeds of livestock, highest in the exotic cattle and lowest in the local cattle and small ruminants (see Senturk, B., & Yalcin, C. 2005). ▪ Analysis of data from an FMD disease outbreak in Sahiwal cattle indicated that 70% of the herd was affected, even though it had been vaccinated previously. Of the cows affected, 69% had reduced milk yields (74 litres) and 74% lost weight (average 18 kg). This herd reportedly experienced six outbreaks of FMD in a fourteen-year period (James, A. D., & Rushton, J. 2002).

Source: Authors on the basis of literature

Evidence from the literature suggest that **milk losses have the largest economic impact**, although it varies between farms, regions and animal species (Chanchaidechachai, T. et al 2022, Jemberu et al. 2016). Milk production is, specifically, found to be higher in high livestock density regions (changes between 30% and 70% depending on animal species and breed) compared to that of low livestock density regions (changes between 15% and 50% depending on animal species and breed). **Draft power losses** are the second most important economic impact (James, A. D., & Rushton, J. 2002 and Jemberu et al. 2016). Overall, the value of production (morbidity) losses is higher than that of mortality losses. This could be attributed to the fact that mortality due to the FMD disease is rare in adult animals (Alhaji, N. B., et al 2020)⁴⁴.

Studies focusing on **smallholders** have indicated substantial economic consequences of FMD, often exceeding 10% of annual household income. The severity of these impacts is influenced by the FMD incidence and the level of dependence on activities affected by the disease (Knight-Jones and Rushton., 2013, Alhaji, N. B., et al 2020). Corporate farms, in particular, may face greater impacts, underscoring the potential benefits of disease control measures for such operations (Hussain et al., 2018).

The economic value of production loss largely varies depending on the **severity of outbreak**, country and year, as witnessed by estimations available from the literature. For example, it was estimated that an outbreak in Ethiopia caused losses of US\$137 per lactating cow and US\$2175 per affected herd (Beyi, 2012). Jemberu et al. (2014) found that herd level impact of an outbreak was US\$76 for Ethiopian crop-livestock farmers. Naipospos et. Suseno (2017) report total economic losses in a year for Indonesia equal to Rp 9.9 trillion (US\$ 761.3 million)⁴⁵. Another example from Australia (Buetre et

⁴⁴ See also <https://www.woah.org/en/disease/foot-and-mouth-disease/#:~:text=Clinical%20signs,-The%20severity%20of&text=Mortality%20is%20generally%20low%20in,period%20is%202%E2%80%9314%20days>.

⁴⁵ Including the loss in cattle production, impacts on trade and on industry including declining domestic cattle price and beef sales as a consequence of the ripple effect, and decrease in tourism expenditures as the spill-over effect

al 2013) shows that in the event of a large multi-state FMD outbreak, revenue losses are estimated between AUD 49.3 billion⁴⁶ and AUD 51.8 billion⁴⁷ (in present value terms over 10 years)⁴⁸.

It is noteworthy to mention that during outbreaks, **farm’s production losses are also exacerbated by trade restrictions**. This results in foregone revenues for both the country affected as well as the FMD-free countries. Restrictions limit the supply of livestock and livestock products to free countries with consequent increase in the market prices for consumers. Even within an endemic country livestock trade is limited; those affected by FMD receive lower prices for their stock and those wishing to purchase animals from FMD free herds face a restricted supply. Furthermore, investment in the livestock sector is limited if there is a perceived risk that FMD may occur (Knight-Jones, T. J. D., & Rushton, J. 2013). Beyond famers, other industries may be positively or negatively affected by FMD outbreaks, depending on their relationship with livestock industries. Existing literature estimates that input providers to FMD-susceptible livestock production (for example, transport, trade and feedstock suppliers) could see reductions in the present value of production of \$11.5 billion over 10 years. Conversely, other industries such as grain and horticulture and their downstream processors may benefit, with an estimated increase in the present value of production of \$15 billion over 10 years, compared with no FMD outbreak. These increases are the result of resources, such as land, being diverted from livestock to other agricultural uses (Buetre, B. et al 2013).

5.2 Cost of existing prevention and control measures

Several measures can be adopted to **prevent and control FMD outbreaks** (see table below for an overview). Some of them are appropriate after an outbreak (e.g. compensation to farmers, culling animals, trade restrictions), while others are better suited as part of the ex-ante surveillance and monitoring system. Overall, the implementation of such measures necessitates a collaboration amongst many diverse stakeholders, with public authorities taking a leading role in coordinating a response. If each farmer acts individually without coordination, areas with poor control can emerge, which undermines overall disease control (Knight-Jones and Rushton, 2013). The same dynamics translates to countries as if one country does not or cannot manage an FMD outbreak, the risk of contagion to other countries grows. This highlights the need for international cooperation in FMD control.

Table 3: Measures to prevent and control a FMD outbreak

	BEFORE	AFTER
Surveillance and monitoring 	Before and after an outbreak, countries may invest in their national surveillance and monitoring systems. Establishing robust surveillance and monitoring systems enables early detection of FMD outbreaks. These systems include regular monitoring of animal health, diagnostic testing, and prompt reporting of potential infections to the authorities. In many countries, FMD is a notifiable disease and vets are legally obliged to report confirmed infections to the government. The FMD virus may then be sequenced to determine whether the virus is of a serotype that is known to be circulating in-country or of a serotype imported from another territory.	

⁴⁶ 25.51 GBP

⁴⁷ 26.80 GBP

⁴⁸ These revenue losses account for around 99% of direct economic costs, with the remaining 1% being the cost of disease control.

	BEFORE	AFTER
<p>Vaccination</p>	<p>Preventive vaccination in areas where the virus might occur can be highly beneficial. Administering vaccines in advance helps establish immunity and lowers the risk of outbreaks. Preventive vaccination can be targeted to high risk areas or across the entire livestock population. Depending on this choice, the cost of control as well as the damages of FMD outbreaks will be different. Moreover, FMD-free countries incur ongoing costs for disease prevention such as maintaining vaccine banks that allow production to ramp up quickly in case of an outbreak.</p>	<p>Vaccination can be used as a control measure to limit virus spread. By vaccinating susceptible animals in affected areas, the disease can be contained, virus shedding can be reduced, and uninfected animals can be safeguarded. Control vaccination could be directed to infected areas (i.e. ring vaccination) as well as to high risk areas around infected areas. In this second case, the strategy aims to create a buffer zone around the outbreak location to prevent further transmission. FMD outbreaks do not only lead to control measures within the outbreak country but may lead to export restrictions imposed by other countries which will have negative economic impacts.-</p>
<p>Farmers' individual actions</p>	-	<p>These include restricting access to livestock and equipment, banning the introduction of new animals to existing herds, regular cleaning and disinfection of livestock pens and equipment, active monitoring and reporting of illness, and proper disposal of manure and carcasses.</p>
<p>Culling animals</p>	-	<p>Infected animals showing clinical signs of FMD are euthanised to eliminate the source of infection. Close contacts of infected animals or those at high risk of contracting the disease may also be culled to prevent further spread. Some governments have also pursued a policy that any cattle living within a several kilometre radius of a confirmed case are slaughtered with the carcasses</p>
<p>Trade bans</p>	-	<p>Implementing restrictions on the movement of livestock, equipment, and vehicles can contain the spread of FMD. Export bans, import restrictions, and certification requirements can hinder the movement of live animals, animal products, and by-products. These trade disruptions can lead to decreased market access, reduced export revenues, and increased costs for compliance with sanitary measures, affecting both producers and the broader economy.</p>
<p>Compensation to farmers</p>	-	<p>Providing financial compensation to affected farmers can mitigate the economic impact of FMD outbreaks. Offering support in terms of veterinary services, guidance, and resources can assist farmers in implementing preventive measures and adopting biosecurity practices</p>

Source: Authors

Evidence from literature shows that the **choice between these different strategies carries significant economic implications** and can greatly influence the management of disease outbreaks and the recovery/maintenance of FMD-free status.

For instance, in Indonesia, an annual investment of Rp 7.7 billion (594,231 USD)⁴⁹ in FMD prevention is necessary to safeguard the country's livestock assets and economy (Naipospos, T. S. P., & Suseno, P. P. 2017). In Southeast Asia, the total costs of a vaccination campaign, including the purchase of vaccines and the logistical requirements of administering the vaccines and monitoring their effectiveness, average US\$4.67 per head per year across all species (cattle, buffalo, pigs, sheep). The cost ranged from US\$2.64 in North Vietnam to US\$9.01 in the Lao PDR (Forman et al 2009). The cost of control increases with the size of an outbreak because more animals must be managed. The total national control costs were estimated by Buetre, B. et al 2013, in Australia, at between AUD 60 million⁵⁰ and AUD 373 million⁵¹ (present values over a 10-years period, small ad multi-state large outbreaks, respectively), with AUD 6.3 million⁵² to AUD 60.2 million⁵³ representing compensation to farmers for animals destroyed during control procedures.

Vaccination and culling strategies are not complementary, and the choice is often dictated by a country's specific needs and cost-benefits considerations. Research indicates that emergency vaccination can be a valuable tool for containing FMD outbreaks, particularly in epidemics. Compared to relying on culling, controlling an outbreak with vaccination is found to be less costly in terms of both direct and indirect agricultural market costs after disease control (Baratt et al., 2019; Bradhurst et al 2019). Also, there are studies indicating that the price and value of livestock output are less affected under vaccination-based strategies than under culling-alone approaches, making vaccination a more favourable option, particularly during severe outbreak situations (Feng et al., 2017). Another factor affecting the choice of vaccination with respect to culling is the response time to the outbreak, as culling may be feasible only at early outbreak stages when relatively few animals have been infected.

Despite its potential benefits, **implementing a vaccination strategy poses challenges**. Current international guidelines discourage a vaccinate-and-retain policy due to longer waiting periods for regaining FMD-free status compared to widespread slaughtering. (Bradhurst, 2019). In regions where FMD-free status is crucial for trade, such as the UK, the impact of disease control strategies on market access and export opportunities becomes a major consideration. In this case, adopting a culling response could allow the county to return to 'FMD-free' status sooner and thereby minimise trade losses. Also, for low-income countries, the costs associated with vaccine procurement and deployment may be unfeasible, especially as current vaccines require two doses per animal per year.

The effectiveness of vaccination strategies depends on the specific context and a country's capacity to manage outbreaks. Countries with strong veterinary services, robust surveillance systems, and rapid response capabilities can better mitigate the short-term impacts of FMD outbreaks and prevent prolonged damages. Conversely, countries lacking effective control measures may face more severe and lasting consequences; these include ongoing outbreaks, trade restrictions, and persistent economic losses (Jemberu et al., 2016, Cabezas et al 2022).

⁴⁹ 469,442 GBP

⁵⁰ 31.05 GBP

⁵¹ 193 GBP

⁵² 3.26 GBP

⁵³ 31.15 GBP

Also, efficient and timely responses are vital in minimising the overall economic consequences of FMD outbreaks. Studies in Scotland reveal that having an initial stock of 200,000 vaccine doses, enough to vaccinate 12% of the cattle population, maximises the benefits of vaccination; while delays in restocking beyond two weeks significantly increase outbreak control costs. Similarly, the evidence from Indonesia indicates that the economic losses from FMD outbreaks rise with longer detection delays, which underlines the need to invest in preparedness measures to enable early detection and response (Porphyre et al., 2018; Naipospos et. Suseno, 2017). However, the issue remains that if control measures are poorly designed or implemented, it can burden stakeholders without effectively reducing disease burden (Knight-Jones et al., 2015).

Trade restrictions are often applied by FMD-free countries to countries experiencing outbreaks. The restrictions can be of different intensity according to national authorities, but must be aligned with the standard WOAH Terrestrial Code⁵⁴. The waiting period required before livestock exports can resume after eradication of an outbreak in a country that is normally 'FMD-free without vaccination' varies depending on whether vaccination was used during the outbreak and the fate of the vaccinated animals, that is if they have been culled (3-month waiting period) or not (6-month waiting period)⁵⁵. As discussed in the previous section, trade restrictions may bring several economic losses to the affected agricultural industry as well as to related industries.

A country's reliance on livestock exports also influences the impact in the event of an FMD outbreak. Countries which are heavily reliant on livestock exports are much more vulnerable, as trade restrictions can disrupt their export markets and revenue streams. Conversely, countries that are not major exporters of livestock and livestock products are less exposed to these risks and trade restrictions cause relatively less economic damage (Naipospos et. Suseno, 2017). FMD-endemic countries can enhance their export potential by developing FMD-free zones or by completely eradicating FMD in-country although such a proposed policy would subject to cost-benefit analyses (Häsler et. al., 2017).

Evidence from literature suggest that the 2001 outbreak in the UK, primarily due to the massive culling of infected and at-risk animals (over 2 million head of livestock) and trade restrictions, caused around 6.5 billion pounds in damages to the British economy, including national governments, farmers, agriculture, food chain and tourist revenues (OIE news, 2021, Thompson et al.,2002, Shanafelt, D. W., & Perrings, C. A. 2017).

While emergency "vaccinate and retain" strategies aid in reducing the spread of FMD and post-outbreak management costs, they elevate trade losses compared to culling because markets remain closed until the virus is entirely eradicated.

5.3 Is vaccination a viable strategy to fight FMD?

Many studies have been conducted in various countries showing that the control and eradication of FMD is an economically viable investment. These studies consider the avoidable losses (discussed in

⁵⁴ The WOAH terrestrial code is available at the following link: https://www.woah.org/en/what-we-do/standards/codes-and-manuals/terrestrial-code-online-access/?id=169&L=1&htmlfile=chapitre_certification_general.htm

⁵⁵ Knight-Jones et al 2016

Section 5.1) as benefits and investment in control and measures (section 5.2) as costs, while the difference between the two as the net benefits.

Alhaji et al 2020 estimated, for instance, that the investment of 463,673 USD (£366,301^[56]) in FMD control yielded a gross return of 15,591,694 USD (£12,317,438^[56]), and a net benefit of 15,128,020 USD (£11,951,136^[56]) in Northern Nigeria. This was equivalent to a net benefit of 24,759 USD (£19,560^[56]) per herd in either of the dairy production systems. The overall benefit-cost ratio (BCR) from the control of FMD in the dairy cattle herds by treatment was 33.6, with slight difference between nomadic pastoral herds (BCR=32.4), and agropastoral herds (BCR=36.6) due to different husbandry system. Ferrari et al (2013) found that the ratio between the estimated economic loss and the cost to prevent the disease in Pakistan is 5.7, meaning that an investment of 1 USD (£0.79^[56]) for the vaccine could potentially save 5.7 USD (£4.5^[56]) of milk loss. In the same country, some years later, benefit cost ratios of animals' vaccination are found by Hussains et al 2017 to be 19.5 and 13.4 for buffaloes and cows in rural areas, respectively (3.1 and 4.8 in peri-urban areas). Jemberu et al 2016 stresses that the strategy of targeted vaccination in Ethiopia, which involves intensive vaccination in high FMD risk areas with ring vaccination and movement restriction during outbreaks in the rest of the country, provides the best economic returns with low risk of loss, and reduces the outbreak incidence rate to the target level within a reasonably short period of time. Truong et al., 2018 reports that investing in FMD prevention in South Vietnam – through a biannual vaccination strategy - can be financially profitable and sustainable for dairy farmers. Ozturk et al 2020 showed that the total net economic impact of a biannual mass vaccination regime and vaccination every 4 months in Turkey is 5,274,836 TL (\$1,094,250) for a population of 800,970 fattening cattle in border cities (which means 76.4 TL, \$15.9, per cattle in Turkey). Interviewees recognises the potential of vaccination strategy in India, the world's largest milk producer. This country has invested a significant amount, 2.5 billion USD (£1.97^[56]) over a five-year period, for FMD vaccines. In contrast, the annual direct loss and the broader impact on the farming sector, has been estimated to be around 3.5 billion USD (£2.76^[56]) in a year.

The viability of investing in a vaccination strategy is also emphasised by STFC report (2010) on the basis of the economic consequences brought about by the 2001 UK outbreak. According to the report, the outbreak's costs were estimated by the UK Department for Environment Food & Rural Affairs (DEFRA) at £8.4 billion. This encompassed losses for agricultural producers (£355 million), losses for the food industry (£170 million), losses for the tourism industry (averaging £3,000 million), indirect costs for supply companies (£2,100 million), and government expenditure on FMDV (£2,800 million). Despite the availability of a vaccine at that time, it was not used due to concerns about its impact on export opportunities. Nevertheless, it has been assessed that if vaccines were employed to prevent future outbreaks, the Synchrotron Radiation Source's contribution to developing these vaccines, though challenging to quantify, would be substantial. Assuming a conservative estimate of just 1% contribution of the knowledge development at synchrotrons to the aforementioned costs, the financial influence would amount to £84 million. In contrast, the research conducted to determine

^[56] This exchange rate is applied throughout the document is based on the exchange rate as on November 20th, 2025: 1 USD = 0.76 GBP.

the X-ray crystal structure using SRS was approximated to involve hundreds of scientists with a value in the tens of thousands of pounds.

The role of vaccination in fighting FMD has been modelled extensively in literature (see for instance Knight-Jones et al 2013, 2015, Bessel et al 2023, Kobayashi et al 2007). A well-established approach, financially supported by the UK Government and other donors, is the one developed by the Global Alliance for Livestock Veterinary Medicines, hereafter GALVmed (see box below).

Box 2 The GALVmed approach to estimate the vaccines' impacts

GALVmed was created in 2008 with the mission to support vaccine production for the major neglected livestock diseases of the developing world. Then, it works with manufacturers and distributors to establish viable vaccine markets. The activity performed by GALVmed, around 30 people, is financially supported by the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, the UK Government, the European Commission, AgResults, Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council, Innovate UK and the Aga Khan Foundation.

In 2019, GALVmed has been selected as the Project Manager for the AgResults FMD Vaccine Challenge Project⁵⁷. This FMD initiative has been designed to encourage the development and uptake of an improved vaccine tailored for the needs of Eastern Africa.

GALVmed approach to value vaccines' impacts relies on three components:

- *Products*: this includes sales of products and the number of animals that are expected to be treated with the product (depending on the different pack sizes).
- *Disease epidemiology*: this comprises the conditions that are treated, number of infections, mortality rates and impact on growth rate.
- *Economics*: this comprises losses from reduced productivity and losses from livestock mortality

This model is employed to estimate the impact of programs that supply pharmaceutical products to address transboundary animal diseases in regions of Africa and South Asia. A schematic diagram of the model framework is shown in the Figure below (source: Bessel et al 2023).

⁵⁷ See <https://www.galvmed.org/news/galvmed-to-manage-multimillion-dollar-agresults-foot-and-mouth-disease-fmd-challenge-project/> and <https://agresults.org/projects/fmd-vaccine>

Source: Authors⁵⁸

Despite the positive findings regarding the importance of adopting a vaccination strategy to fight FMD, there is a broad agreement in the literature (see for instance Robinson et al., 2016, Porta et al., 2013, Hardham et al., 2020, Doel, 2003, Diaz-San Segundo et al., 2017) as well as among the interviewees that the current type of vaccines, mostly of inactivated nature⁵⁹, exhibit various constraints, especially in terms of production, transportation, administration, coverage and efficiency (see box below for more details). All these drawbacks reduce the accessibility of the FMD vaccines and the efficacy of vaccination campaigns, especially in Asia and Africa.

Box 3 The limitations of inactivated vaccines

Production: inactivated vaccines are created from a killed version of the virus which is obtained by using chemical or physical agents that destroy infectivity while retaining immunogenicity so they are able to stimulate an immune response. This adds complexity to the production process and requires specialised facilities (e.g. maintained under negative air pressure, using HEPA filters, autoclave drain destroying any material before entering the public sewage system, etc.) which minimise the risk of virus escape⁶⁰.

⁵⁸ On the basis of <https://www.galvmed.org/> and https://www.galvmed.org/galvmedat10/GALVmed_at_10.pdf See also Bessel et al 2023

⁵⁹ All the current production plants are listed on the following website: <https://www.foot-and-mouth.org/fmd-vaccine-producers>

⁶⁰ More information available on the following document: https://www.woah.org/fileadmin/Home/eng/Media_Center/docs/pdf/Disease_cards/Q_A-FMD-EN.pdf

Transportation: inactivated vaccines retain the thermal instability of the virus itself, necessitating cold-chain storage and transportation to maintain potency. This creates logistics challenges and high costs to distributing vaccines.

Administration: During the vaccine formulation process, incomplete virus inactivation can induce disease in vaccinated animals.

Coverage: While a single vaccine can include several serotypes of FMD virus, there is no guarantee of protection against all strains within those serotypes. The effectiveness of the vaccine may vary against different strains of the virus, reducing its overall efficacy. Also, the protection provided by a primary course of vaccination typically lasts for around 6 months. This necessitates frequent booster doses to maintain immunity, increasing the cost and effort required for vaccination programs.

Efficacy: The control of the disease requires the ability to distinguish between infected and vaccinated animals. Typically, this differentiation is achieved by detecting serum antibodies to viral non-structural proteins (NSP). However, even purified vaccine preparations may contain traces of NSP, potentially resulting in false-positive results in vaccinated animals and complicating the differentiation process. An additional layer of concern relates to the variability in vaccine quality which can lead to differences in the efficacy of the vaccines produced by different providers or at different production sites. Variations in production techniques, raw materials, and quality assurance practices may result in vaccines with varying immunogenicity and effectiveness, making it challenging to ensure consistent protection across different vaccine sources. The interviewees stated that LMICs (most of which are endemic countries) are particularly prone to this risk, reducing the effectiveness of the vaccination campaigns.

Source: Authors on the basis of desk research⁶¹ and interviewees

The VLP vaccine – that has been studied at Diamond - addresses these limitations. In the following section, its main advantages as well as challenges for its introduction into the market are outlined on the basis of the evidence collected through interviews and desk research.

⁶¹ See for instance Robinson et. al., 2016, Porta et. al., 2013, Hardham et. al., 2020, Doel, 2003, Diaz-San Segundo et. al., 2017

6. THE VLP VACCINE: ADVANTAGES AND CHALLENGES

After a brief introduction of the new vaccine generation – developed to overcome the limitations of existing inactivated vaccines, this Section focuses on the VLP vaccine whose development Diamond has contributed to, by outlining main advantages and anticipate challenges related to its introduction into the market. Ultimately, this section makes an attempt to estimate the benefits associated with a hypothetical scenario, exploring the potential advantages if the VLP vaccine were utilised to vaccinate potentially infected animals.

6.1 New vaccines generation

Both literature and interviews suggest three main new generation of vaccines which have been developed so far to overcome the shortcomings of inactivated vaccines and to enhance global FMD control. These include: VLPs vaccines, adenovirus vaccines, and peptide vaccines. Their features are briefly described in the following table.

Table 4: New generation of vaccines

NEW VACCINE	DESCRIPTION
VLP vaccines	They resemble the virus capsid structure but do not contain viral nucleic acid making them completely safe. VLPs retain the epitope distribution of natural virus particles and stimulate the production of neutralising antibodies in the same way thus providing good protection. These empty capsids can be produced in culture (bacteria, mammalian cells, insect cells or plants) and then be given as a vaccine. In the case of the vaccine considered for this report, various laboratory techniques (called recombinant) are used to synthesise the capsids, which consists in allowing for a spontaneous assembling of parts of the virus (the P1 structural protein precursor and the 3C protease) ⁶² . These VLPs are engineered to contain stabilizing mutations that do not affect their immunogenicity but extend their shelf life and reduce dependence on a cold chain. The interval between boosters may also be extended which makes adherence to a vaccination protocol easier. There are no NSPs so they can be distinguished by the DIVA test which should ease regulations around trade limitations. They do not need to be produced in containment so they can be produced cheaply in production plants close to the area of need including in LMICs. Multivalent vaccines can be produced and adapted to circulating strains.
Adenovirus vaccines	They are a form of VLP but makes uses of human adenovirus of type 5 as a vector to produce FMD VLPs within host cells. A candidate vaccine using an adenovirus vector for FMD was developed by researchers at the United States Department of Agriculture ⁶³ . The adenovirus-vectored FMD vaccine is safer and more efficient than traditional vaccines. It only uses a portion of the FMDV genome, which means it cannot cause disease. This eliminates the need for high-security facilities and reduces costs. Animals vaccinated with this vaccine can be easily distinguished from infected ones through tests. Additionally, the adenovirus-vectored FMD vaccine is more stable during production compared to traditional vaccines, which can undergo antigenic changes due to their replication method (Fernandez-Sainz et al., 2017). Compared to VLP vaccines, adenovirus vaccines might

⁶² Porta et. al., 2013

⁶³ <https://www.avma.org/javma-news/2012-08-01/fmd-vaccine-first-allowed-be-made-us>

NEW VACCINE	DESCRIPTION
	experience difficulties in the development of multivalent vaccines, making it more difficult to protect against multiple serotypes.
Peptide vaccines	They mimic well-defined B- and T-cell epitopes of the FMD virus, which can induce FMD protection. While simple linear peptide vaccines have shown limited effectiveness, scientists developed methods to improve them. FMD peptide vaccines offer flexibility in adapting to different virus strains. They have the potential to provide effective protection with a single dose, making them cost-effective and suitable for rapid emergency responses (Forner et. al., 2021). The main challenge that comes with peptide vaccines is their low immunogenicity as they do usually not trigger an immune response that is enough strong to protect the animals

Source: Authors

The vaccine developed by Diamond belongs to the VLP vaccine typology. Evidence gathered from interviews and literature point to different advantages related to VLP vaccine over traditional inactivated vaccines as well as some challenges which should be overcome to maximise its potential. These are summarised in what follows.

6.2 VLP advantages

Safer, less expensive and more accessible. VLP vaccine is made of small synthetic protein shells, called 'virus like particles' (VLPs), which mimic the FMDV outer shell, without using its genome (in contrast to inactivated vaccines), and so stimulate an immune response. This characteristic enhances safety as it eliminates the risk of virus escape. Additionally, VLP vaccines do not require DEFRA category 4 facilities for production, which are known for being expensive in terms of both machinery and human resources. The reduced production costs associated with VLP vaccines can lead to increased vaccine supply, particularly in countries where FMD is endemic and currently relies on vaccine imports. As noted by one interviewee, lower production costs enable the establishment of new manufacturing capacity, making vaccines more accessible and affordable for countries. VLP vaccines also allow for the development of additional vaccine doses for the same production cost (input goods), thus resulting in higher yield.

Easier storage and transportation. VLP vaccines exhibit less heat sensitivity, providing farmers with more flexibility in the time between taking the vaccine from storage and its administration. Unlike other inactivated FMD vaccines, the VLPs do not require high containment facilities for production (see previous paragraph) and have been engineered to remain stable up to temperatures of 56°C, reducing reliance on cold-chain transport and storage. This reduces the risk of vaccine spoilage, contributing to streamlined vaccination campaigns and broader coverage in FMD-prone areas. Moreover, VLP vaccines can be stored and transported more easily in regions with an unreliable cold chain, thereby reducing the complexity and cost of transportation from producers to purchasers. This feature is particularly significant in countries with an endemic status lacking a local FMD vaccine manufacturing facility, such as LMICs.

Faster response to outbreaks. Inactivated vaccines involve a lengthy process of adaptation to cell culture possibly up to a year. This extended timeline before inactivated vaccines can be produced contributes to an average response time of 12 to 15 months from detecting a new variant to

developing new vaccines. VLP vaccines are produced by a different method and in cases where existing stabilising strategies can be used, a new vaccine strain could be produced rather more quickly reducing the response time. This accelerated response is deemed crucial, as even a two-week delay in implementing control measures can result in significant cost increases. Additionally, the production of VLP vaccines can be rapidly expanded to meet increased demand during outbreaks, utilising manufacturing facilities initially designed for non-FMD VLP vaccines, thereby enabling a swift and effective response to emerging challenges, particularly during outbreaks in FMD-free countries.

More reliable diagnosis between infected and vaccinated animals. The complete absence of some viral proteins from the VLP vaccine enables a clear differentiation between uninfected animals, animals with vaccine-related antibodies, and those with infection-derived antibodies, thus ensuring a more accurate and reliable diagnostic tool. This could have significant impact on culling policies

- *After the VLP vaccine has been introduced into the market, it offers a faster response to new strains or serotypes compared to inactivated vaccines, as the entire process of adapting to tissue culture becomes unnecessary. Adapting inactivated vaccines to new strains typically takes approximately 1.5 years, involving the time required for virus growth in a cell culture and subsequent inactivation processes.*
- *VLP vaccines do not contain the virus, so should not be produced in high containment facilities which are expensive to build and maintain, driving up the cost.*
- *We can store VLPs at elevated temperatures, tolerating up to 56 degrees Celsius for 23 hours. If there is a break in the cold chain at 56 degrees C, it remains stable.*
- *With the current generation of vaccines, the DIVA diagnosis can be done but is also limited given its high potential of error. Inactivated DIVA vaccines rely on purification, which doesn't achieve a 100% accuracy in differentiation. VLP technology offers a 100% DIVA capability, making it easier to certify uninfected animal*
- *Unlike the traditional vaccines, there is no chance that the empty shell vaccine could revert to an infectious form. This work will have a broad and enduring impact on vaccine development, and the technology should be transferable to other viruses from the same family, such as poliovirus and hand foot and mouth disease, a human virus which is currently endemic in South-East Asia*

Quotes from interviews

The table below presents a summary of the distinctions identified between inactivated vaccines and the new generation counterparts. While highlighting the evident advantages of the new generation vaccines over the inactivated ones, the table also underscores that the VLP vaccine ensures protection across different strains and serotypes.

Table 5: Inactivated vs. new generation of vaccine

CHARACTERISTICS	INACTIVATED	ADENOVIRUS	PEPTIDE	VLP
Heat-sensitive	Yes	No	No	No
Cross-strain/serotype protection	Yes	No	No	Yes
High biosecurity level of manufacturing	Yes	No	No	No

CHARACTERISTICS	INACTIVATED	ADENOVIRUS	PEPTIDE	VLP
Level and length of protection	Equal to new vaccines	Equal to inactivated	Mostly lower than inactivated	Equal to inactivated
Fast development of vaccines for new strains	No	Yes	Yes	Yes

Source: Authors based on literature and interviews

6.3 VLP current challenges

Despite their advantages, some challenges exist for an extensive deployment of VLP vaccines.

Being supported and recommended by relevant institutions. WOAHA currently acknowledges inactivated vaccines as a possible option for FMD vaccination campaigns. However, it explicitly mentions that live attenuated vaccines are not acceptable due to the risk of infection development post-vaccination. VLP vaccines are instead completely safe. To become popularised, it will be essential to include them in the possible options suggested by high-level governance actors like WOAHA, which can reduce the scepticism of national purchasers in buying them.

Entailing the risk of transition from inactivated to VLP production processes. Switching production facilities from inactivated vaccines to VLP vaccines poses significant challenges for companies. Existing production facilities for inactivated vaccines lack the necessary tools for VLP vaccine production. Consequently, adapting production processes or establishing new facilities comes with substantial initial costs associated with VLP-specific production technologies. Interviewees noted that companies interested in producing different vaccine types would face the obligation to change their facilities, incurring high initial costs, despite the potential long-term cost benefits. However, investing in new factories for VLP production would be much cheaper and less prone to risks compared to potential outbreaks stemming from inactivated vaccine production facilities. Governments may raise awareness regarding the mitigation of risks and provide incentives or support mechanisms to ease this transition.

Enhancing protection capacity. Current FMDV vaccines based on inactivated virus can be multivalent and it is envisaged that a new VLP vaccine would be tetravalent.

- *One of the challenges faced by low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) is producing and procuring sufficient quantities of high-quality vaccines. They may produce vaccines locally, but the quality is often subpar, necessitating the importation of vaccines during outbreaks. With VLP vaccines, these countries might be able to have local vaccine.*
- *One of the main conditions for the spread of these vaccines is that companies will be willing to transfer the technologies especially as the technology is quite transferable. Thus, there is the risk of ending up like Covid vaccine situation, where these vaccines will not be used because of IP matters. However, all the funding agencies involved required technology transfer as part of their funding award.*
- *Another conditionality for these vaccines to be beneficial concerns if they are provided at a reasonable cost. It needs to be competitive on costs with conventional vaccines, especially because current FMD vaccines are relatively inexpensive compared to vaccines for other animal diseases.*

- *Large-scale manufacturing is deemed crucial to truly understand the capabilities, costs, and advantages of the VLP technology.*
- *Producing the VLP vaccine should be feasible from a technical point of view. The main challenge lies in competing with low prices in certain markets (e.g. South America)*
- *The Gates Foundation, through advanced market commitments and policy advocacy, plays a role in bridging the gap between government policy changes and the company's commitment to providing vaccines. The complex scenario involves negotiations between both parties.*
- *India seeks 1.3 billion vaccines annually, posing a potential market for the new vaccine technology. However, there is uncertainty about the company's willingness to enter such markets, emphasising the need for a different mindset and partner model.*
- *The biggest benefit, in my view, is the opening of manufacturing facilities in places where they currently do not exist. This addresses the critical issue of supply, allowing governments to invest in national control programs and set up manufacturing facilities throughout their countries.*
- *Many African countries lack a streamlined or straightforward system for product licensing, and their regulatory processes can be quite intricate and time-consuming. In some of these countries, the regulatory authorities may not be equipped to handle novel or advanced technologies. Standardisation is crucial for vaccine efficacy*
- *The main challenges of development of the VLP vaccine is to adapt the vaccine to other more complex serotypes, as the stability of the existing vaccine is highly compromised. Multiple VLP vaccines may be needed for different strains/serotypes of foot-and-mouth disease. one single vaccine product can be a combination of vaccines against multiple strains/serotypes.*

Quotes from interviews

6.4 What if?

As part of our assessment, we provide an estimate of the net benefits brought about by a “what if scenario”, consisting of the introduction of the VLP vaccine into the market.

For the purpose of this estimation, we rely on the GALVmed approach (see Box 3 in Section 5.3 for details)⁶⁴ and, specifically, we compared the cost of preventing/controlling FMD through the administration of VLP-FMD vaccine against its benefits in terms of number of infections averted and, therefore, avoided production losses. In compliance with the GALVmed approach, our calculation mostly depends on three factors: the number of VLP doses administered (*product sales*), the number of infections averted (*disease*), the value of production loss (*economics*). It is worth pointing out that our estimate only considers the production losses avoided while disregarding all other economic losses occurring in the case of an outbreak, such as losses of revenues to the agricultural industries and related sectors (e.g. tourism and transport) as discussed in Section 5.1.

⁶⁴ The decision to employ this model for assessing the impact of the VLP-FMD vaccine was informed by a literature review of existing models for vaccine evaluation as well as by interviews with Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation. An alternative model that was discussed internally was the one developed by Knight Jones and Rushton (2013) which estimates the total cost of FMD for all endemic countries by multiplying the average cost of infection with the number of animals infected in one year. However, the GALVmed approach was deemed to be most suitable for the purpose of our analysis since specifically designed to estimate the impact of pharmaceutical products and considering the number of vaccine doses sold – for which an estimation was available from interviews - as the primary factor influencing the reduction of cases.

As a general consideration for our estimation, we assume that **VLP administered doses are substitutes of existing vaccines** (whereas this number may be lower): basing on the key advantage of the VLP vaccine, which has the potential to enhance availability in areas where the current vaccine is inaccessible for price or production reasons (see Section 6.2 for more details), we assume that VLP administered are a proportion of the total number of FMD vaccine administered in all endemic countries (in total 94), excluding Indonesia. Specifically, we assumed a market penetration share of 20% in line with suggestions from interviews⁶⁵. This market share has been applied to an estimated total market of 2.35 billion vaccines, (as reported by Knight Jones and Rushton, 2013 and approximately confirmed by interviews).

Table 6 An overview of our estimation

Cost of administration <i>(in a year)</i>	(a) <u>Number of vaccine administered in a year:</u> 20% of the total number of vaccine administered in a year (2.35 billion) = 470,000,000 (all species) (b) <u>Cost of administering one dose of vaccine:</u> 4.67 USD ⁶⁶ Cost of administration (a*b)= 2.2 billion USD⁶⁷
Avoided production losses <i>(in a year)</i>	(a) Number of animals treated with VLP vaccine: 20% of total number affected by FMD (1.8 billion) = 370,238,182 (b) Number of avoided infections (avoided infections * treated animals) = 0.07 * 370,238,182 = 24,915,729 (c) Production losses: 140 USD ⁶⁸ per animal Avoided production losses (b*c) = 3.5 billion
Net benefit <i>(in a year)</i>	Avoided production losses – Cost of administering the VLP vaccine = 1.3 billion USD⁶⁹
B/C ratio	1.59

A detailed description of the variables considered for our estimation and underlying assumptions is provided in Annex 1.

As a result of our estimation, the potential **net benefits** of commercialising the VLP vaccine in all endemic countries amount to **1.3 billion USD in a year. A B/C ratio equal to 1.59 is found**, thus meaning that an investment of 1 USD⁷⁰ for the vaccine could potentially save 1.59 USD⁷¹.

⁶⁵ It is worth stressing that, in principle, the model can be used for a scenario analysis with changes in different parameters.

⁶⁶ 3.69 GBP
⁶⁷ 1.74 GBP
⁶⁸ 110.6 GBP
⁶⁹ 1.03 GBP
⁷⁰ 0.79 GBP
⁷¹ 1.26 GBP

In addition, we estimated the benefits brought about by the VLP vaccine over a 10-years period. By applying a discount rate of 3% (suggested by existing guidelines)⁷², we find a present net value of VLP benefits equal to **11 billion USD**⁷³.

7. CONCLUSIONS

FMD is one of the most infectious viruses that humans are aware of and it can have **significant economic impacts when outbreaks occur**. Economic impacts are primarily driven by reduced milk and meat production but there are also long-term downstream impacts in terms of reduced traction power from infected animals. This disproportionately impacts subsistence farmers in LMICs where FMD is endemic. Any mass FMD outbreak is also likely to result in trade restrictions being imposed against the country in question to guard against contagion, especially from countries that hold 'FMD-free' status.

As examined in this case study, one of the major challenges to managing FMD is that there are at least seven known major serotypes under surveillance and **immunity to one serotype does not guarantee immunity to other serotypes**. Many countries have therefore developed policies to exclude FMD from their territory entirely, but this does come with the consequence that an outbreak does lead to widespread culling policies. International coordination is primarily provided by the World Organisation for Animal Health, which has produced a series of protocols to assist countries with an FMD outbreak and to classify countries based on the level of FMD circulation.

Vaccines against the virus exist but come with the challenges that:

1. they require live virus contained under high level biosafety protocols to produce,
2. these vaccines cannot allow vaccine and virus-induced immunity types to be distinguished, and
3. this vaccine is relatively heat sensitive which is an issue in countries with unreliable cold chain.

Current policy within FMD-free countries has continued an elimination strategy and while outbreaks do occur, this has allowed a suspension of vaccine programmes. It is considered impossible to eradicate FMDV entirely worldwide as native animals act as virus reservoirs, such as the African Buffalo in Sub-Saharan Africa. New vaccine technologies exist that could mitigate the weaknesses summarised above. These include VLPs, adenovirus, and peptide vaccines.

This case study provided an assessment of a new VLP vaccine developed by MSD through a collaboration between Oxford (including Diamond) and Reading Universities and the Pirbright Institute. The evaluation has been drawn from a review of existing literature and interviews with experts in this field and stakeholders involved in the development of the vaccine under assessment. The evaluation yielded the following findings:

⁷² EC 2014, 2021

⁷³ 8.69 GBP

- Both existing literature and interviewees recognise that **VLP vaccines have practical advantages over traditional inactivated vaccines**: They do not have the same issues with thermal instability, potentially lower cross-strain protection limitations, and complex production requirements. They do not require high-biosafety facilities to produce, enhancing safety and reducing production costs. VLP vaccines also streamline logistics with easier storage and transportation, especially in regions without local vaccine manufacturing. Their potentially faster response to evolving virus variants is pivotal in curbing economic losses during FMD outbreaks. However, their acceptance hinges on regulatory recognition and industry willingness to invest in new production facilities. Understanding these nuances is key to shaping effective vaccination strategies.
- Members of both the collaboration and the broader research community interviewed for this study **acknowledged the pivotal role played by Diamond in the vaccine development process**. They highlighted specific features of Diamond that distinguish it from other facilities in the landscape, including: 1) the unique combination of equipment available to researchers, especially the complementarity between Diamond's X-ray crystallography and electron microscopy facilities, 2) the capability of Diamond's facilities to collect data from crystals in-situ (i.e directly from sealed crystallization plates), 3) the highly skilled workforce at Diamond, 4) Diamond's proactive and intensive approach to user-facility collaborations. These distinctive features of Diamond set it apart from other facilities and offer opportunities for further development in future vaccine research.
- Our simulation – based on the use of the GALVmed approach – showed that the introduction of **VLP vaccines to the market could yield benefits in the form of avoided production losses**. Specifically, starting from the hypothesis that the market penetration share of the VLP-FMD vaccine is equal to 20% (of the total number of vaccines administered), the potential net benefits per year in all endemic countries is estimated to be 1.3 billion USD⁷⁴ in a year. The B/C ratio of this commercialisation amounts to 1.59. Over a 10-year period, the associated net benefits of introducing VLPs amounts to 11 billion USD⁷⁵.
- Our estimate should be considered as conservative since it only considers the avoided production losses brought about by the introduction of the VLP vaccine without considering the additional losses (e.g. to affected industries) which are mentioned in the GALVmed approach. To confirm this, interviewees recognised that the available data may significantly underestimate the actual number of infections per year. This suggests that the true costs of the disease are likely to be much higher than identified in this report, and consequently, **the potential net benefits of the VLP vaccine could be even greater**.

⁷⁴ 1.03 GBP

⁷⁵ 8.69 GBP

ANNEX 1. ESTIMATING THE BENEFITS OF THE VLP VACCINE: UNDERLYING ASSUMPTIONS

The table below provides a detailed explanation of the variables considered for the purpose of our estimation and underlying assumptions. It's noteworthy that, for the analysis conducted over the 10-year period, all the variables described below were treated as constants for the sake of prudence.

Table 7: Our estimation: underlying assumptions

Variables	Explanation
COST OF CONTROL/PREVENTION = Number of doses administered * cost of administering one dose	
Number of doses administered:	<p style="text-align: center;">Number of VLP doses administered = VLP doses sold * product utilisation rate</p> <hr/> <p>Dose sold: this number was unknown and considered a sensitive information by interviewees. Therefore, we calculated it by making assumptions on the market share of the VLP-FMD vaccine over the total number of vaccine doses administered.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Dose sold: VLP-FMD vaccine share/total number of vaccine administered</p> <p>The share of VLP-FMD vaccine was assumed to 20% on the basis of interviewees.</p> <p>The total number of vaccine doses was estimated to be 2.35 billion per year on the basis of Knight-Jones, T. J. D., & Rushton, J. (2013). This value is referred to 2011 year.</p> <p>Product utilisation rate: it represents the share of sold vaccine doses which are actually administered, taking into account the potential losses during transportation and injection processes. This information is not available for the specific case of VLP-FMD vaccine since field tests have not been carried out so far. The GALVMED model originally assigns a 90% utilisation rate to all its products, including live attenuated and inactivated vaccines for various diseases (such as Fowl Pox or Newcastle diseases). However, assuming that the VLP is easier to use and to transport as compared to inactivated vaccines, we assume that all doses sold are administered (utilisation rate=100%).</p>
Cost of administering one dose of Vaccine	<p>As discussed in Section 5.2, this cost varies from country to country and can increase in the case of outbreak since more animals should be managed. Drawing from the literature (Forman et al 2009) and assuming that the vaccine is administered in a non-outbreak period, we assumed this value to be equal to US\$4.67 per head per year across all species (cattle, buffalo, pigs, sheep). This cost includes the purchase of vaccines and the logistical requirements of administering them and monitoring their effectiveness.</p>

Variables	Explanation
AVOIDED PRODUCTION LOSSES = Number of infected animals avoided * Value of production losses per each animal	
Number of infected animals avoided	<p>This number is derived as follows</p> <p style="text-align: center;">(1) Total number of animals affected by FMD * (2) Share of animals treated with VLP-FMD vaccine * (3) Share of infections averted.</p> <p>In what follows, more details on the assumptions related to each of these variables is provided.</p>
	<p>(1) Total number of animals for a particular country per year is taken from the database of the FAO "Crops and livestock production"⁷⁶. The database contains data from 1961 to 2021 for all types of animals affected by FMD (buffalos, cattle, swine, goats and sheep). The total number of animals in 2021 endemic countries, excluding Indonesia, amounted to 5 billion, encompassing buffalos, cattle, goats, sheep, and pigs.</p> <p>When converting the number of animals into livestock units (LSUs), the total becomes 1.8 billion LSUs, distributed among buffalos (10%), cattle (45%), goats and sheep (11%), and pigs (33%).</p>
	<p>(2) Share of animals treated with VLP-FMD vaccine:</p> <p>This is assumed to be 20% in compliance with the share of doses of VLP-FMD vaccine sold into the market.</p>
	<p>(3) Infection averted = Product efficacy * [1 - (1 - (Annual Incidence * Duration of protection)^(1 / Years between outbreaks))]</p> <p>This variable represents the number of cases averted thanks to the utilisation of a single doses of the vaccine. Its estimation depends on the probability of the animal becoming infected, which is a function of disease incidence, duration of protection from the vaccination and years between outbreaks.</p> <p>It is found to be 0.07 in a year. To estimate this number the following variables were considered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Annual incidence: this variable was assumed to be equal to 10% for all the endemic countries. This assumption relies on the evidence gathered by Knight-Jones, T. J. D., & Rushton, J. (2014) and interviews. It can be considered a conservative assumption if considering that studies on FMD in endemic countries in Asia and Africa suggest a higher estimation, infection rates of at least one third of cattle annually, and in some cases, rates as high as 70-90%⁷⁷ ○ Duration of protection (years): This variable refers to the time a single dose of the VLP vaccine protects the animal. Interviewees remarked that there is no difference between inactivated and VLP vaccines. The duration of protection of inactivated vaccines has been retrieved from the literature on FMD as well as from the information provided by sellers of inactivated vaccines (Peta et al., 2021; Paton et al., 2019; AFTOGEN® by Biogenesis Bagò). The value assigned to this variable is equal to 0.5 (e.g. 6 months). It is important to stress that only high quality of inactivated FMD vaccines trigger a reaction that is high enough to last 6 months.

76 <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QCL>

77 <https://cgspace.cgiar.org/bitstream/handle/10568/52319/GFRA%20newsletter%20no%203.pdf>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Years between outbreaks: This variable represents the probability of reinfection of the same animal in one year and it depends on the country example. The database used to estimate the value attributed to this variable is FAOSTAT “Crops and livestock production”⁷⁸, which reports the number of outbreaks per single administrative units for every country in every year. Given that the duration of immunity provided by the infection is around 7.5 months, the minimum value assigned to this variable cannot be below 0.625 (7.5/12) and is assigned when the average number of outbreaks in the administrative units are higher than 1.6 (El-Sayed, E., et al 2012). Therefore, years between outbreaks is equal to $\text{Max}(0.625, 1/\text{number of outbreak per year})$. The value included in our model is equal to 0.66 and has been calculated as the average number of years between outbreaks occurring in the endemic countries. ○ Product efficacy is considered as the share of vaccine doses that provide effective protection against FMD. According to information obtained from interviews, the efficacy of VLP-FMD vaccine is similar to that of inactivated vaccines. For our analysis, this value was assumed to be 90% based on papers provided by the World Reference Lab for FMD⁷⁹ assessing the potency testing of inactivated vaccines.
Average cost of infection per animal	For the purpose of our estimation, we relied on the average cost of production losses calculated by Knight-Jones, T. J. D., & Rushton, J. (2013) which refers to all endemic countries and is equal to 100 dollars in 2011 and 140 dollars⁸⁰ in 2021 (adjusted by using the global inflation rate).

Source: Authors

⁷⁸ <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QCL>

⁷⁹ <https://www.foot-and-mouth.org/vaccines/fmd-vaccine-potency-testing#references>

⁸⁰ 110.76 GBP

ANNEX 2. PATENTS' CITATION ANALYSIS

In the following, we define the knowledge generated by Diamond direct users as level 0 publications (P0) and knowledge generated by those citing ALBA publications as level 1 publications (P1). Similarly, we define patent documents citing level 0 publications as level 0 patents (Pat0) and patent documents citing level 1 publications as level 1 patents (Pat1).

The database used as basis for this analysis was built according to the following procedure. Scientific publications generated by the Diamond direct users, P0, were provided by Diamond, and consists in **11 papers published between 2009 and 2018**. Starting from this set of documents, P1 publications were identified combining the results of a search on Web of Science and Google Scholar. These two online resources allow the identification of scientific papers citing a given publication. While Web of Science results are more consistent and restricted to peer reviewed articles, the results obtained using Google Scholar are wider, and were therefore cleaned to exclude duplicates and students' theses. Finally, P0 publications which were citing other P0 publications, and therefore would have fallen within the definition of P1 as well, were excluded from the P1 set, in order to avoid double counting. In this way **474 unique P1 publications** (456 without self-citation⁸¹) were identified. Note that 97 (90 without self-citations) of those P1 publications were citing more than one P0 article.

Next, we used the Lens PatCite tool⁸² to identify the patents that cite scientific publications of levels 0 and 1. Starting from the papers' DOI⁸³ we identified **30 Pat0 patents (citing 7 P0 publications) and 164 Pat1 patents (citing 69 P1 publications)**. Note that 20 of the Pat1 patents were also Pat0 patents, (i.e., were citing both a first and a second wave publication).

Publications and patents documents of level 0

8 out of the 11 first wave papers authored by Diamond direct users were cited by 30 patents, out of which 15 are granted patents and the other 15 are patent applications. For each cited P0 publications the number of patents citing it widely varies. The article "Rational engineering of recombinant picornavirus capsids to produce safe, protective vaccine antigen" by Porta, C. et al. (2013)⁸⁴ was cited by 20 distinct patents, belonging to 13 distinct families⁸⁵. Four of the P0 publications instead were cited by 1 patent. Below the matches between P0 papers (summarised by the author and publication year) and Pat0 patents (patents' keys) are visualised. Only two patents cited two distinct P0 articles. In addition to this also the two previous technical steps linked to the publication are visualised. Looking at the right of the figure below, each of the authors of the publication exploited one or more beamlines (a total of 5 beamlines were used by the authors). Three of these beamlines were in turn associated with 6 proposals.

⁸¹ Self-citation were defined as those P1 publications, whose author, or co-author, was the main author of the P0 publication cited in that P1 article.

⁸² <https://www.lens.org/>. Lens is the world's largest open and free data platform of the global patents and scholarly articles.

⁸³ The digital object identifier is a persistent identifier widely used to identify academic, professional, and government information, such as journal articles, research reports and data sets.

⁸⁴10.1371/journal.ppat.1003255

⁸⁵ As from the European Patent Office "A patent family is a collection of patent applications covering the same or similar technical content. The applications in a family are related to each other through priority claims."

Figure 4: Matches between P0 (left hand side) and Pat0 (right hand side)

Source: own elaboration on Lens PatCite results

The 8 articles - cited by the 30 patents - are classified into a relatively wide number of subject categories, which mainly pertain to the fields of microbiology, molecular biology and general chemistry and biochemistry.

Table 8 The first wave of publications cited by patents

Author	Title	Year	Cited by patent count	Citing family count
Porta, C. et al.	Rational engineering of recombinant picornavirus capsids to produce safe, protective vaccine antigen	2013	20	13
Kotecha, A. et al.	Structure-based energetics of protein interfaces guides foot-and-mouth disease virus vaccine design	2015	4	2
Mousnier, A. et al.	Fragment-derived inhibitors of human N-myristoyltransferase block capsid assembly and replication of the common cold virus	2018	3	3

Scott, K. A. et al.	SAT2 foot-and-mouth disease virus (FMDV) structurally modified for increased thermostability	2017	2	2
Borley, D. W. et al.	Evaluation and use of in-silico structure-based epitope prediction with foot-and-mouth disease virus	2013	1	1
Swatek, K. N. et al.	Irreversible inactivation of ISG15 by a viral leader protease enables alternative infection detection strategies	2018	1	1
Kotecha, A. et al.	Rules of engagement between $\alpha\beta6$ integrin and foot-and-mouth disease virus	2017	1	1
Malik, N. et al.	Structures of foot and mouth disease virus pentamers: Insight into capsid dissociation and unexpected pentamer reassociation	2017	1	1

Source: Lens PatCite results

As far as the patents are concerned they belong to 4 distinct jurisdictions: 14 granted patents have their jurisdiction in the United States, while one was filed under the European Patent Office. Regarding the 15 patent applications instead, 14 have been filed under the international patent system while one under the Korean Patent Office.

The figures below display some of the characteristics of the patents. Firms are the largest patent owner (with 11 patents). If we look only at the granted patents instead, public institutes rank first with 6 granted patents. It is worth underlining that firms and private institutes are mainly active in the healthcare sector. Looking at the patent owners (considering only the granted patents), the top owner is "The Government of the US Secretary of Homeland Security" with five patents, followed by the "Pirbright Institute" with three.

Concerning the sectors of application, the patents are classified using the Cooperative Patent Classification (CPC)⁸⁶. Looking at the 3rd hierarchical level (sub-classes), it is evident that the patents mostly pertain to the same sectors of application. In particular 28 out of 30 Pat0 documents fall into the A61K subclass: "Preparations for medical, dental, or toilet purposes". 24 and 23 patents instead are classified respectively into the sectors A61P, "Specific therapeutic activity of chemical compounds or medicinal preparations" and C12N, "Microorganisms or enzymes; compositions thereof; propagating, preserving, or maintaining microorganisms; mutation or genetic engineering; culture media".

⁸⁶ The CPC is a hierarchical system of classification jointly managed by the European Patent Office and the US Patent and Trademark Office.

Figure 5: Number of patents by type of patent owner

Figure 6: Top granted patents owners

Figure 7: Number of patents (granted and applications) by sectors of application (CPC classification)

Source: Own elaboration on Lens PatCite data

Finally, it is worth underlining that five patents publication display among the inventors the authors of the related P0 publications. Interestingly these patents and (some of) their inventors are linked to only two first wave publications (see Figure below).

Figure 8: Matches between authors of P0 publications (left-hand side) and Pat0 patents (right hand side)

Source: own elaboration on Lens PatCite results

Publication and patent documents of level 1

As pointed out above, as second wave publications **474 unique articles were identified**. Out of these, 69 were mentioned in 164 distinct patents (90 patent application and 73 granted patents, while for one patent the status is unknown). In the figure below the matches between publications (green dots) and patents (red dots) are displayed. The number of patent citations per article ranges from 1 (orange circle in the middle of the figure), to 13 (blue circle). In particular the P1 article with the highest number of patent citation is “Adjuvants for foot-and-mouth disease virus vaccines: recent progress” (Cao, Y., 2014)⁸⁷. The 13 patents that cite it belong to 6 distinct families. Looking at the number of distinct citing families instead, two P1 articles rank better: “Mapping Putative [B-Cell Zika Virus NS1 Epitopes Provides Molecular Basis for Anti-NS1 Antibody Discrimination between Zika and Dengue Viruses](#)” (Freire, M. et al., 2017)⁸⁸ with 8 citing families (and 11 citing patents) and “Antibody specific

87 10.1586/14760584.2014.963562

88 10.1021/acsomega.7b00608

epitope prediction-emergence of a new paradigm" (Sela-Culang, I. et al., 2015)⁸⁹ with 7 citing families (and 9 citing patents).

In 19 cases the Pat1 documents mention more than one P1 articles. Most of them can be found in the red circle, where the patent⁹⁰ citing the largest number of article (five) is displayed.

Figure 9: Matches between P1 (green dots) and Pat1 (red dots)

Source: Own elaboration of Lens PatCite results with Gephi software.

The second wave patents were filled under eight distinct jurisdictions. Interestingly almost all the granted patents are under the United States jurisdiction, while all under the international patent system we find only patent applications (see Figure below).

89 10.1016/j.coviro.2015.03.012

90 Genetically engineered Foot and Mouth Disease Virus and related proteins, polynucleotides, compositions, methods and systems, US_10953085_B2

Figure 10: Number of patents by jurisdiction

Source: Own elaboration of Lens PatCite data.

Concerning the sector of application, as for Pat0 patents, in the Figure below the number of patents of the ten most common CPC sub-classes is displayed. The sectors of application are mostly the same found for Pat0 patents. In particular 83% of the patents fall in the A61K subclass, while 76% and 67% are classified into the A61P and C12N sectors respectively. Finally, while among Pat0 patents none falls into the G16B sub-class “Bioinformatics, i.e. information and communication technology specially adapted for genetic or protein-related data processing in computational molecular biology”, among the second wave patents we find 8.

Figure 11: Number of patents (granted and application) by CPC sector

Source: own elaboration on Lens PatCite data.

ANNEX 3. BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Acharya, R., Fry, E., Stuart, D., Fox, G., Rowlands, D., & Brown, F. (1989). The three-dimensional structure of foot-and-mouth disease virus at 2.9 Å resolution. *Nature*, 337(6209), 709–716. <https://doi.org/10.1038/337709a0>
- Alhaji, N. B., Amin, J., Aliyu, M. B., Mohammad, B., Babalobi, O. O., Wungak, Y., & Odetokun, I. A. (2020). Economic impact assessment of foot-and-mouth disease burden and control in pastoral local dairy cattle production systems in Northern Nigeria: A cross-sectional survey. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, 177, 104974. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2020.104974>.
- Allan, D. R., Collins, S. P., Evans, G., Hall, D., McAuley, K., Owen, R. L., Sorensen, T., Tang, C. C., von Delft, F., Wagner, A., & Wilhelm, H. (2015). Status of the crystallography beamlines at Diamond Light Source. *The European Physical Journal Plus*, 130(3), 56. <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjp/i2015-15056-x>
- Argonne, 2021. Advanced Photon Source helps Pfizer create COVID-19 antiviral treatment | Argonne National Laboratory [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.anl.gov/article/advanced-photon-source-helps-pfizer-create-covid19-antiviral-treatment> (accessed 11.17.23).
- Barasa, M., Catley, A., Machuchu, D., Laqua, H., Puot, E., Tap Kot, D., & Ikiror, D. (2008). Foot-and-mouth disease vaccination in South Sudan: Benefit-cost analysis and livelihoods impact. *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases*, 55, 339-351.
- Bessell, P. R., Salmon, G., Schnier, C., Tjasink, K., Al-Riyami, L., & Peters, A. (2023). A high level estimation of the net economic benefits to small-scale livestock producers arising from animal health product distribution initiatives. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2023.1171989>
- Bradhurst, R., Garner, G., East, I., Death, C., Dodd, A., & Kompas, T. (2019). Management strategies for vaccinated animals after an outbreak of foot-and-mouth disease and the impact on return to trade. *PloS one*, 14(10), e0223518. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0223518>
- Bravo de Rueda, C., de Jong, M.C., Eblé, P.L., Dekker, A., 2014. Estimation of the transmission of foot-and-mouth disease virus from infected sheep to cattle. *Veterinary Research* 45, 58. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1297-9716-45-58>
- Buetre, B., Wicks, S., Kruger, H., Millist, N., Yaiinshet, A., Garner, G., ... & Symes, M. (2013). Potential socio-economic impacts of an outbreak of foot-and-mouth disease in Australia. Australian Bureau of Agricultural and Resource Economics and Sciences. Research Report 13.11. Canberra, ACT.
- Cabezas, A. H., Mapitse, N. J., Tizzani, P., Sanchez-Vazquez, M. J., Stone, M., & Park, M. K. (2022). Analysis of suspensions and recoveries of official foot and mouth disease free status of WOAHS Members between 1996 and 2020. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 9, 1013768.
- Cao, Y., Lu, Z., & Liu, Z. (2016). Foot-and-mouth disease vaccines: progress and problems. *Expert review of vaccines*, 15(6), 783–789. <https://doi.org/10.1586/14760584.2016.1140042> Cao et. al. (2016),

“Foot-and-mouth disease vaccines: progress and problems”, *Expert Rev Vaccines*, doi: 10.1586/14760584.2016.1140042

Chanchaidechachai, T., Saatkamp, H., & Inchainri, C. (2022). Analysis of Epidemiological and Economic Impact of Foot-and-Mouth Disease Outbreaks in Four District Areas in Thailand. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 9, Article 904630. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2022.904630>

Catalano, G., López, G. G., Sánchez, A., & Vignetti, S. (2021). *From scientific experiments to innovation: Impact pathways of a Synchrotron Light Facility*. *Annals of Public and Cooperative Economics*, <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/apce.12322>

Catalano, G., Florio, M., Garcia, G., Pancotti, C., Sánchez Grueso, A. and Vignetti, S. (2020), *The pathways from experiments to innovation impacts: evidence from ALBA Synchrotron Light Facility report prepared in the framework of the RI-PATHS project* (Grant Agreement number: 777563) available at https://www.albasynchrotron.es/en/industry/csil-alba_report_final.pdf

Colenutt, C., Brown, E., Nelson, N., Paton, D. J., Eblé, P., Dekker, A., Gonzales, J. L., & Gubbins, S. (2020). Quantifying the Transmission of Foot-and-Mouth Disease Virus in Cattle via a Contaminated Environment. *mBio*, 11(4), e00381-20. <https://doi.org/10.1128/mBio.00381-20>

Curry, S., Fry, E., Blakemore, W., Ghazaleh, R. A., Jackson, T., King, A., Lea, S., Newman, J., Rowlands, D., & Stuart, D. (1996). Perturbations in the surface structure of A22 Iraq foot-and-mouth disease virus accompanying coupled changes in host cell specificity and antigenicity. *Structure*, 4(2), 135–145. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0969-2126\(96\)00017-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0969-2126(96)00017-2)

Diamond Light Source. (2020). Welcome to I24— Diamond Light Source. <https://www.diamond.ac.uk/Instruments/Mx/I24.html>

Diamond Light Source. (2022). Titan Krios— Diamond Light Source. <https://www.diamond.ac.uk/Instruments/Biological-Cryo-Imaging/eBIC/Instruments/KRIOS.html>

Diamond news Article (2013). Foot-and-mouth-disease vaccine. Available at: https://www.diamond.ac.uk/Home/News/LatestNews/27_03_13.html

Diamond News Article (2019). Pirbright Institute grants a new licence for FMDV vaccine development. Available at: <https://www.diamond.ac.uk/Home/News/LatestNews/2019/02-09-2019.html>

Diaz-San Segundo, F., Medina, G. N., Stenfeldt, C., Arzt, J., & de los Santos, T. (2017). FOOT-AND-MOUTH DISEASE VACCINES. Published by Elsevier. Available at: [Foot-and-mouth disease vaccines - ScienceDirect](https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0950268817333333)

Dickson, D. (1997). £10 million pledged for UK synchrotron source. *Nature*, 389(6649), Article 6649. <https://doi.org/10.1038/38560>

Doel T. R. (2003). FMD vaccines. *Virus research*, 91(1), 81–99. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0168-1702\(02\)00261-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0168-1702(02)00261-7)

Doré, A.S. et al. (2014) 'Structure of class C GPCR metabotropic glutamate receptor 5 transmembrane domain', *Nature*, 511(7511), pp. 557–562. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature13396>.

Duran, D., Couster, S. L., Desjardins, K., Delmotte, A., Fox, G., Meijers, R., Moreno, T., Savko, M., & Shepard, W. (2013). PROXIMA 2A – A New Fully Tunable Micro-focus Beamline for Macromolecular Crystallography. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 425(1), 012005. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/425/1/012005>

El-Sayed, E., Mossad, W., Ali, S. M., & Shawky, M. (2012). Studies on the duration of immunity induced in cattle after natural FMD infection and post-vaccination with bivalent oil vaccine. *Veterinary World*, 5(10), 603-608. doi: 10.5455/vetworld.2012.603-608. Published Online: 29-07-2012. Available at: <https://www.veterinaryworld.org/Vol.5/October%202012/Studies%20on%20the%20duration%20of%20immunity%20induced%20in%20cattle.pdf>

ESFRI, 2021. Roadmap 2021 - Strategy Report on Research Infrastructures.

ESRF. (2022). ID30A-1 / MASSIF-1. <https://www.esrf.fr/MASSIF1>

ESRF. (2023a). ID23-1: Gemini - Macromolecular Crystallography. https://www.esrf.fr/UsersAndScience/Experiments/MX/About_our_beamlines/ID23-1

ESRF. (2023b). ID30A-3 / MASSIF-3. https://www.esrf.fr/home/UsersAndScience/Experiments/MX/About_our_beamlines/id30a-3--massif-3.html

European Commission (2014). Guide to cost-benefit analysis of investment projects. Economic appraisal tool for Cohesion Policy. https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/docgener/studies/pdf/cba_guide.pdf

European Commission (2021). Economic Appraisal Vademecum 2021-2027 - General Principles and Sector Applications. https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/information/publications/guides/2021/economic-appraisal-vademecum-2021-2027-general-principles-and-sector-applications

FAO and WOAHA (2018). The Progressive Control Pathway for Foot and Mouth Disease control (PCP-FMD) Principles, Stage Descriptions and Standards. Available at: <https://rb.gy/7xcea>

Feng S, Patton M and Davis J (2017). Market Impact of Foot-and-Mouth Disease Control Strategies: A UK Case Study. *Front. Vet. Sci.* 4:129. doi: 10.3389/fvets.2017.00129

Fernandez-Sainz, I., Medina, G. N., Ramirez-Medina, E., Koster, M. J., Grubman, M. J., & de los Santos, T. (2017). Adenovirus-vectored foot-and-mouth disease vaccine confers early and full protection against FMDV O1 Manisa in swine. *Virology*, 502, 123-132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.virol.2016.12.021>.

Ferrari, G., Tasciotti, L., Khan, E., & Kiani, A. (2013). Foot-and-mouth disease and its effect on milk yield: An economic analysis on livestock holders in Pakistan. *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases*, Advance online publication. doi:10.1111/tbed.1207

Forman, S., Le Gall, F., Belton, D., Evans, B., François, J. L., Murray, G., Sheesley, D., Vandersmissen, A., & Yoshimura, S. (2009). Moving towards the global control of foot and mouth disease: an opportunity for donors. *Revue Scientifique et Technique (WOAH)*, 28, 883-896.

Forner, M., Cañas-Arranz, R., Defaus, S., de León, P., Rodríguez-Pulido, M., Ganges, L., Blanco, E., Sobrino, F., & Andreu, D. (2021). Peptide-Based Vaccines: Foot-and-Mouth Disease Virus, a Paradigm in Animal Health. *Vaccines*, 9(5), 477. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9050477>

Fry, E. E., Lea, S. M., Jackson, T., Newman, J. W. I., Ellard, F. M., Blakemore, W. E., Abu-Ghazaleh, R., Samuel, A., King, A. M. Q., & Stuart, D. I. (1999). The structure and function of a foot-and-mouth disease virus-oligosaccharide receptor complex. *The EMBO Journal*, 18(3), 543-554. <https://doi.org/10.1093/emboj/18.3.543>

Fry, E. E., Newman, J. W. I., Curry, S., Najjam, S., Jackson, T., Blakemore, W., Lea, S. M., Miller, L., Burman, A., King, A. M. Q., & Stuart, D. I. (2005). Structure of Foot-and-mouth disease virus serotype A1061 alone and complexed with oligosaccharide receptor: Receptor conservation in the face of antigenic variation. *Journal of General Virology*, 86(7), 1909-1920. <https://doi.org/10.1099/vir.0.80730-0>

Fry, E., Acharya, R., & Stuart, D. (1993). Methods used in the structure determination of foot-and-mouth disease virus. *Acta Crystallographica Section A: Foundations of Crystallography*, 49(1), 45-55. <https://doi.org/10.1107/S0108767392005737>

Galli, S., 2014. X-ray Crystallography: One Century of Nobel Prizes. *J. Chem. Educ.* 91, 2009-2012. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ed500343x>

Global Foot-and-Mouth Disease Research Alliance (2018). Gap Analysis Report.

Govindaraj, G., Ganesh Kumar, B., Krishnamohan, A., Raveendra Hegde, Nanda Kumar, Kokila Prabhakaran, Vinay Mohan Wadhwan, Naresh Kakker, T. Lokhande, Krishna Sharma, Amit Kanani, Limaye, Natchimuthu K., Ananth PN, Arup Kumar De, Tanveer Ahmed Khan, Jyoti Misri, BB Dash, Bramhadev Pattnaik, Rahman Habibur (2021). Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) incidence in cattle and buffaloes and its associated farm-level economic costs in endemic India. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, 190, 105318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2021.105318>.

Grant, R. (2018). Cryo-Electron Microscopy [Text]. <https://www.bioc.cam.ac.uk/facilities/cryo-electron-microscopy>

Hamond, J. (2011). FMD Vaccine: Practical Applications from an International Perspective-FMDV Vaccine to Live. An event organised by NFUS, Moredun, and Scottish Government, 15 March 2011.

Hardham, J. M., Krug, P., Pacheco, J. M., Thompson, J., Dominowski, P., Moulin, V., Gay, C. G., Rodriguez, L. L., & Rieder, E. (2020). Novel Foot-and-Mouth Disease Vaccine Platform: Formulations for Safe and DIVA-Compatible FMD Vaccines With Improved Potency. *Frontiers in veterinary science*, 7, 554305. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2020.554305>

Häsler, B., Limon, G., Queenan, K., Rushton, J., Madege, M., Mlangwa, J., & Mghwira, J. (2021). Cost-benefit and feasibility analysis for establishing a foot-and-mouth disease free zone in Rukwa region

in Tanzania. Preventive veterinary medicine, 196, 105494.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2021.105494>

Hussain, A., Abubakar, M., Shah, H., Arshed, M. J., Hussain, M., & Afzal, M. (2017). Socioeconomic Impact of Foot and Mouth Disease Vaccination in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Life and Social Sciences*, 15(3), 183-191.

James, A. D., & Rushton, J. (2002). The economics of foot and mouth disease. *Revue scientifique et technique (International Office of Epizootics)*, 21, 637-644.

Jemberu W.T. et al. (2016). Cost-benefit analysis of foot and mouth disease control in Ethiopia. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, Volume 132, Pages 67-82.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2016.08.008>.

Jemberu, W. T., Mourits, M. C., Woldehanna, T., & Hogeveen, H. (2014). Economic impact of foot and mouth disease outbreaks on smallholder farmers in Ethiopia. *Preventive veterinary medicine*, 116(1-2), 26-36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2014.06.004>

Juanhuix, J., Gil-Ortiz, F., Cuní, G., Colldelram, C., Nicolás, J., Lidón, J., Boter, E., Ruget, C., Ferrer, S., & Benach, J. (2014). Developments in optics and performance at BL13-XALOC, the macromolecular crystallography beamline at the Alba Synchrotron. *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*, 21(4), 679-689.
<https://doi.org/10.1107/S160057751400825X>

Jungbluth, S., Depraetere, H., Slezak, M., Christensen, D., Stockhofe, N., Beloeil, L. (2022). A gaps-and-needs analysis of vaccine R&D in Europe: Recommendations to improve the research infrastructure. *Biologicals*, 76, 15-23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biologicals.2022.02.003>.

Kamel, M., El-Sayed, A., & Castañeda Vazquez, H. (2019). Foot-and-mouth disease vaccines: recent updates and future perspectives. *Archives of virology*, 164(6), 1501-1513.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00705-019-04216-x>

Knight-Jones, T. J. D., & Rushton, J. (2013). The economic impacts of foot and mouth disease – What are they, how big are they and where do they occur? *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, 112(3-4), 161-173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2013.07.013>.

Knight-Jones, T. J. D., McLaws, M., & Rushton, J. (2015). Foot-and-Mouth Disease Impact on Smallholders - What Do We Know, What Don't We Know and How Can We Find Out More? *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases*.

Knight-Jones, T. J. D., McLaws, M., & Rushton, J. (2017). Foot-and-Mouth Disease Impact on Smallholders - What Do We Know, What Don't We Know and How Can We Find Out More? *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases*, 64(4), 1079-1094. doi: 10.1111/tbed.12507.

Knight-Jones, T. J., Robinson, L., Charleston, B., Rodriguez, L. L., Gay, C. G., Sumption, K. J., & Vosloo, W. (2016). Global Foot-and-Mouth Disease Research Update and Gap Analysis: 2 - Epidemiology, Wildlife and Economics. *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases*, 63(Suppl 1), 14-29. doi: 10.1111/tbed.12522. PMID: 27320163.T.J.D.

Knight-Jones, T. J., Robinson, L., Charleston, B., Rodriguez, L. L., Gay, C. G., Sumption, K. J., & Vosloo, W. (2016a). Global Foot-and-Mouth Disease Research Update and Gap Analysis: 1 - Overview of Global Status and Research Needs. *Transboundary and emerging diseases*, 63 Suppl 1, 3–13. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.12528>

Kobayashi, M., Carpenter, T. E., Dickey, B. F., & Howitt, R. E. (2007). A dynamic, optimal disease control model for foot-and-mouth-disease:: II. Model results and policy implications. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, 79(2-4), 274-286.

Kotecha, A., Perez-Martin, E., Harvey, Y., Zhang, F., Ilca, S. L., Fry, E. E., Jackson, B., Maree, F., Scott, K., Hecksel, C. W., Harmsen, M. M., Mioulet, V., Wood, B., Juleff, N., Stuart, D. I., Charleston, B., & Seago, J. (2018). Chimeric O1K foot-and-mouth disease virus with SAT2 outer capsid as an FMD vaccine candidate. *Scientific Reports*, 8, 13654. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-31856-x>

Kotecha, A., Seago, J., Scott, K., Burman, A., Loureiro, S., Ren, J., Porta, C., Ginn, H., Jackson, T., Perez-Martin, E., Siebert, C., Paul, G., Huiskonen, J., Jones, I., Esnouf, R., Fry, E., Maree, F., Charleston, B., & Stuart, D. (2015). Structure-based energetics of protein interfaces guides foot-and-mouth disease virus vaccine design. *NATURE STRUCTURAL & MOLECULAR BIOLOGY*, 22(10), 788–794. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nsmb.3096>

Lea, S., Abu-Ghazaleh, R., Blakemore, W., Curry, S., Fry, E., Jackson, T., King, A., Logan, D., Newman, J., & Stuart, D. (1995). Structural comparison of two strains of foot-and-mouth disease virus subtype O1 and a laboratory antigenic variant, G67. *Structure*, 3(6), 571–580. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0969-2126\(01\)00191-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0969-2126(01)00191-5)

Logan, D., Abu-Ghazaleh, R., Blakemore, W., Curry, S., Jackson, T., King, A., Lea, S., Lewis, R., Newman, J., Parry, N., Rowlands, D., Stuart, D., & Fry, E. (1993). Structure of a major immunogenic site on foot-and-mouth disease virus. *Nature*, 362(6420), Article 6420. <https://doi.org/10.1038/362566a0>

Lyons, N. A., Afzal, M., Toirov, F., Irshad, A., Bartels, C. J. M., & Rushton, J. (2021). Economic Considerations for Advancement Through the Progressive Control Pathway: Cost-Benefit Analysis of an FMD Disease-Free Zone in Punjab Province, Pakistan. *Frontiers in veterinary science*, 8, 703473. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2021.703473>

Malito, E., Carfi, A., & Bottomley, M. J. (2015). Protein Crystallography in Vaccine Research and Development. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 16(6), 13106-13140. doi: 10.3390/ijms160613106. PMID: 26068237; PMCID: PMC4490488.

Martin-Garcia, J. M., Botha, S., Hu, H., Jernigan, R., Castellví, A., Lisova, S., Gil, F., Calisto, B., Crespo, I., Roy-Chowdhury, S., Grieco, A., Ketawala, G., Weierstall, U., Spence, J., Fromme, P., Zatsepin, N., Boer, D. R., & Carpena, X. (2022). Serial macromolecular crystallography at ALBA Synchrotron Light Source. *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*, 29(3), 896–907. <https://doi.org/10.1107/S1600577522002508>

McCarthy, A. A., Barrett, R., Beteva, A., Caserotto, H., Dobias, F., Felisaz, F., Giraud, T., Guijarro, M., Janocha, R., Khadrouche, A., Lentini, M., Leonard, G. A., Lopez Marrero, M., Malbet-Monaco, S.,

McSweeney, S., Nurizzo, D., Papp, G., Rossi, C., Sinoir, J., ... Mueller-Dieckmann, C. (2018). ID30B – a versatile beamline for macromolecular crystallography experiments at the ESRF. *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*, 25(4), 1249–1260. <https://doi.org/10.1107/S1600577518007166>

Midlands Innovation. (2023). Cryo. <https://midlandsinnovation.org.uk/cryo>

Mitchell Crow, J. (2021, August 31). The must-have multimillion-dollar microscopy machine. *Nature Index*. <https://www.nature.com/nature-index/news/must-have-multimillion-dollar-microscopy-machine-cryo-em>

Mohamad, A., Shaari, N. F., & Hamzah, H. Z. (2023). Impact of Foot and Mouth Disease on Cattle Production in Peninsular Malaysia. *Journal of Sustainability Science and Management*, 18(5), 143-150.

Naipospos, T. S. P., & Suseno, P. P. (November 2017). Cost Benefit Analysis of Maintaining FMD Freedom Status in Indonesia. Report submitted to the World Organisation of Animal Health (WOAH).

NAO. (2002). The 2001 Outbreak of Foot and Mouth Disease—National Audit Office (NAO) report. National Audit Office (NAO). <https://www.nao.org.uk/reports/the-2001-outbreak-of-foot-and-mouth-disease/>

Nicholls, D.J. *et al.* (2008) 'Identification of a Putative Intracellular Allosteric Antagonist Binding-Site in the CXC Chemokine Receptors 1 and 2', *Molecular Pharmacology*, 74(5), pp. 1193–1202. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1124/mol.107.044610>.

Orsel, K., de Jong, M.C.M., Bouma, A., Stegeman, J.A., Dekker, A., 2007. The effect of vaccination on foot and mouth disease virus transmission among dairy cows. *Vaccine* 25, 327–335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2006.07.030>

Orsel, K., Dekker, A., Bouma, A., Stegeman, J.A., Jong, M.C.M. de, 2005. Vaccination against foot and mouth disease reduces virus transmission in groups of calves. *Vaccine* 23, 4887–4894. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2005.05.014>

Ozturk, N., Kocak, O., & Vosough Ahmadi, B. (2020). Economic Analysis of Increasing Foot-and-Mouth Disease Vaccination Frequency: The Case of the Biannual Mass Vaccination Strategy. *Frontiers in veterinary science*, 7, 557190.

Paton, D. J., Reeve, R., Capozzo, A. V., & Ludi, A. (2019). Estimating the protection afforded by foot-and-mouth disease vaccines in the laboratory. *Vaccine*, 37(37), 5515-5524. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2019.07.102>

Peta, F. R. M., Sirdar, M. M., van Bavel, P., Mutowembwa, P. B., Visser, N., Olowoyo, J., Seheri, M., & Heath, L. (2021). Evaluation of Potency and Duration of Immunity Elicited by a Multivalent FMD Vaccine for Use in South Africa. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 8, 750223. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2021.750223>

- Porphyre, T., Rich, K. M., & Auty, H. K. (2018). Assessing the Economic Impact of Vaccine Availability When Controlling Foot and Mouth Disease Outbreaks. *Frontiers in veterinary science*, 5, 47. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2018.00047>
- Porta, C., Kotecha, A., Burman, A., Jackson, T., Ren, J., Loureiro, S., ... & Charleston, B. (2013). Rational engineering of recombinant picornavirus capsids to produce safe, protective vaccine antigen. *PLoS pathogens*, 9(3), e1003255.
- Porta, C., Xu, X., Loureiro, S., Paramasivam, S., Ren, J., Al-Khalil, T., Burman, A., Jackson, T., Belsham, G. J., Curry, S., Lomonossoff, G. P., Parida, S., Paton, D., Li, Y., Wilsden, G., Ferris, N., Owens, R., Kotecha, A., Fry, E., ... Jones, I. M. (2013). Efficient production of foot-and-mouth disease virus empty capsids in insect cells following down regulation of 3C protease activity. *JOURNAL OF VIROLOGICAL METHODS*, 187(2), 406–412. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jviromet.2012.11.011>
- Robinson, A. L. (2015). History of Synchrotron Radiation. *Synchrotron Radiation News*, 28(4), 4–9. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08940886.2015.1059228>
- Robinson, L., Knight-Jones, T. J. D., Charleston, B., Rodriguez, L. L., Gay, C. G., Sumption, K. J., & Vosloo, W. (2016). Global foot-and-mouth disease research update and gap analysis: 3 – Vaccines. *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases*, 63(Suppl. 1), 30–41.
- Seago, J., Jackson, T., Doel, C., Fry, E., Stuart, D., Harmsen, M., Charleston, B., & Juleff, N. (2012). Characterization of epitope-tagged foot-and-mouth disease virus. *JOURNAL OF GENERAL VIROLOGY*, 93, 2371–2381. <https://doi.org/10.1099/vir.0.043521-0>
- Senturk, B., & Yalcin, C. (2005). Financial impact of foot-and-mouth disease in Turkey: Acquisition of required data via Delphi expert opinion survey. *Veterinárni medicína*, 50(10), 451-460.
- Şentürk, B., Yalçın, C., Şenturk, B., & Yalcin, C. (2008). Production losses due to endemic foot-and-mouth disease in cattle in Turkey. *Turkish Journal of Veterinary and Animal Sciences*, 32, 433-440.
- Shanafelt, D. W., & Perrings, C. A. (2017). Foot and mouth disease trade in live animals. *Rev. Sci. Tech. Off. Int. Epiz.* Retrieved from <https://www.woah.org/app/uploads/2021/03/01112017-00114-en-shanafelt.pdf>
- Shankar, B., Morzaria, S., Fiorucci, A., & Hak, M. (2012). Animal disease and livestock-keeper livelihoods in Southern Cambodia. *International Development Planning Review*, 34, 39-63.
- Singh, R. K., Sharma, G. K., Mahajan, S., Dhama, K., Basagoudanavar, S. H., Hosamani, M., Sreenivasa, B. P., Chaicumpa, W., Gupta, V. K., & Sanyal, A. (2019). Foot-and-Mouth Disease Virus: Immunobiology, Advances in Vaccines and Vaccination Strategies Addressing Vaccine Failures-An Indian Perspective. *Vaccines*, 7(3), 90. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines7030090>
- Sobrino, F., Blanco, E., García-Briones, M., & Ley, V. (1999). Synthetic peptide vaccines: Foot-and-mouth disease virus as a model. *Developments in Biological Standardization*, 101, 39–43.

Sobrino, F., Sáiz, M., Jiménez-Clavero, M., Núñez, J., Rosas, M., Baranowski, E., & Ley, V. (2001). Foot-and-mouth disease virus: A long known virus, but a current threat. *Veterinary Research*, 32(1), 1–30. <https://doi.org/10.1051/vetres:2001106>

Stenfeldt, C., Pacheco, J. M., Brito, B. P., Moreno-Torres, K. I., Branan, M. A., Delgado, A. H., Rodriguez, L. L., & Arzt, J. (2016). Transmission of Foot-and-Mouth Disease Virus during the Incubation Period in Pigs. *Frontiers in veterinary science*, 3, 105. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2016.00105>

STFC. (2010). *New Light on Science: The Social & Economic Impact of the Daresbury Synchrotron Radiation Source, (1981—2008)*. Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC). <https://www.ukri.org/publications/new-light-on-science-socioeconomic-impact-study-of-daresbury-srs/>

STFC. (2017, March 23). *Sci-Tech Daresbury Campus impact study*. <https://www.ukri.org/publications/sci-tech-daresbury-campus-impact-study/>

Sultanov, A. A., Tyulegenov, S., Yessebekova, G. N., Berdikulov, M. A., Mukhanbetkaliyev, Y., Akhmetzhanova, A., Perez, A. M., & Abdrakhmanov, S. K. (2023). The progressive control of foot-and-mouth disease (FMD) in the Republic of Kazakhstan: Successes and challenges. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 10, Article 1036121. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2023.1036121>

Sumption, K., Rweyemamu, M., & Wint, W. (2008). Incidence and distribution of foot-and-mouth disease in Asia, Africa and South America; combining expert opinion, official disease information and livestock populations to assist risk assessment. *Transboundary and emerging diseases*, 55(1), 5–13. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1865-1682.2007.01017.x>

Sutmoller, P., Barteling, S. S., Olascoaga, R. C., & Sumption, K. J. (2003). Control and eradication of foot-and-mouth disease. *Virus Research*, 91, 101-144.

Thompson, D., Muriel, P., Russell, D., Osborne, P., Bromley, A., Rowland, M., Creigh-Tyte, S., & Brown, C. (2002). Economic costs of the foot and mouth disease outbreak in the United Kingdom in 2001. *Revue scientifique et technique (International Office of Epizootics)*, 21(3), 675–687. <https://doi.org/10.20506/rst.21.3.1353>

Truong, D. B., Goutard, F. L., Bertagnoli, S., Delabouglise, A., Grosbois, V., & Peyre, M. (2018). Benefit-Cost Analysis of Foot-and-Mouth Disease Vaccination at the Farm-Level in South Vietnam. *Frontiers in veterinary science*, 5, 26. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2018.00026>

University of Birmingham. (2022). *GUIDANCE NOTE 5: TRANSPORT OF BIOLOGICAL MATERIALS BY ROAD, RAIL OR AIR*. <https://intranet.birmingham.ac.uk/hr/documents/public/hsu/hsuguidance/guidance-note-5-transport-2022.pdf>

WOAH (2009). *WOAH Terrestrial Manual – Foot-and-Mouth Disease Chapter*. Available at : [https://www.woah.org/fileadmin/Home/eng/Animal Health in the World/docs/pdf/2.01.05_FMD.pdf](https://www.woah.org/fileadmin/Home/eng/Animal_Health_in_the_World/docs/pdf/2.01.05_FMD.pdf)

WOAH (2022). Resolution No. 11. <https://www.woah.org/en/disease/foot-and-mouth-disease/#ui-id-2>)

WOAH (2022). Resolution No. 12. (<https://www.woah.org/en/disease/foot-and-mouth-disease/#ui-id-2>)

WOAH news (2021). Reflections on the Foot-and-Mouth Disease Epidemic of 2001: a United Kingdom Perspective. WOA Bulletin.

WOAH. FMD – Questions and Answers. Accessed on 6 October 2023. Available at : https://www.woah.org/fileadmin/Home/eng/Media_Center/docs/pdf/Disease_cards/Q_A-FMD-EN.pdf.

World Reference Laboratory for Foot-and-Mouth Disease (2023), Quartely report Jan-Mar 2023, Available at: <https://www.wrlfmd.org/ref-lab-reports>.

Wungak, Y. S., Olugasa, B. O., Ishola, O. O., Lazarus, D. D., & Ularamu, G. H. (2016). Foot-and-mouth disease (FMD) prevalence and exposure factors associated with seropositivity of cattle in north-central, Nigeria. African Journal of Biotechnology, 15(24), 1224-1232. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5897/AJB2016.15332>